

D4.8

Report on current and good practices for design and control of hybridGEOTABS buildings

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Executive Summary

The study of hybridGEOTABS buildings, how they are designed and controlled is at the heart of WP₄ with demonstration and case study buildings serving as real and virtual test beds. These buildings and what we can learn from them are here to assist the (design and control) concept development taking place in WP₂ and WP₃. A review of what can be observed today in Europe is needed to further understand the issues different stakeholders are facing. Current and best practices gathered from projects around Europe are described in this report. The design of hybridGEOTABS buildings as a whole, but also the design of the individual core modules (ground source heat exchanger (GSHX), heat pump (HP) and Thermally Activated Building Systems (TABS)) and their level of control and integration as it is done today are described in more detail in this deliverable. The report gives the reader an overview of the latest development for controlling integrated building systems using model predictive control (MPC) and how this technology can accelerate to the decarbonisation of heating and cooling and shape the future of building services.

This report is a public deliverable and should help the readers to understand the current problems related to the design and control of hybridGEOTABS buildings. "hybridGEOTABS" refers to the utilisation of hybrid energy sources on the supply side (one source being always geothermal) as well as hybrid on the room side (emission side) with a secondary fast reacting system complementing the TABS. Thanks to our cross disciplinary consortium, with practical commercial experience in different regions of Europe, we have investigated the current and best practice for design and controls of such systems. Additionally, the latest development in model predictive control are investigated in this report in order to understand where this research project is willing to take the building services industry in a near future. For ease of understanding "current practice" refers in this report to GEOTABS or hybridGEOTABS buildings with rule based controller, not necessarily properly tuned and most of the time not commissioned properly. In those cases, the secondary production is always based on fossil fuel resources. Then we identified Good (or Best) practice and with this term we refer to carefully and well-sized hybridGEOTABS buildings and systems, with RBC development and commissioning according to state-of-the-art rules.

In order to produce high quality designs, HVAC engineers face many challenges during feasibility and pre-design. We have observed the design process for feasibility and pre-design and noticed some similar behaviour throughout engineering and consultancy practise. Mainly the lack of any detailed information and too many assumptions leads to inefficient, oversized and therefore not competitive GEOTABS HVAC installations including the geothermal boreholes, which represent the highest investment cost. The feasibility stage for instance is the time to investigate different building solutions and weigh them against each other. At this stage, the full potential of this concept in terms of energy, greenhouse gas emission savings and life cycle costs should be clearly exposed to enable the client to take a fair and well-informed decision for his building.

The main challenge is the lack of technical guidance to perform a correct and fast sizing calculation, which can assess the optimal share of GEOTABS resources in this hybrid mix. Due to the thermal inertia of the TABS and the complexity of system integration, solving this question usually involves running a dynamic load simulation of the entire building and systems to test the right solution and eventually prove the viability of the concept to the client. This is time consuming and very expensive for the design team at this stage of the process (feasibility study).

In practice we observed that, although the advantages of thermally activated building structures using low exergy renewable sources, are well known in the research and development world as well as for some architects, designers and construction firms, still a lot of work remains to be done in order to facilitate the market uptake of this concept. The hybridGEOTABS technology as a “plug and play” package is a huge step forward from GEOTABS building in a way that it can overcome any operational obstacles previously found with GEOTABS. However, from a design perspective, the introduction of hybrid sources and emission systems into one building operational concept increases the level of complexity. Until now, some HVAC designers have realised the potential of these hybrid concepts and try to design and implement them. The early design phases, in which they use rule of thumbs, in-house experience, data from the literature etc., is followed by the detailed design, in which expensive simulation work is used to validate their concepts, if the clients are supportive of this. For the engineering practice, this is a highly inefficient way to work, which is clearly not sustainable on a commercial basis and would therefore deter many specialists from renewing the experience on another project.

To provide some guidelines for designing hybridGEOTABS, a sizing methodology, more specifically a load splitting algorithm and a sizing and decision making tool, are developed in this project. In the sizing methodology, the share of GEOTABS, covering the heating and cooling baseload, and the share of the secondary system, covering the residual load are found. Based on the maximum of both loads, both systems are sized. The sizing process is done for numerous cases in Europe and general guidelines for sizing hybridGEOTABS are developed.

At the beginning of a building project, important architectural decisions should be considered, which will also influence the degree of hybridity in the concept, the other more obvious factors being the availability of the resources and in the internal heat gains from the type of use. For instance, best practice in architecture and building physics aim at minimising the peaks of the heating and cooling loads by reducing heat losses and gains, providing adequate solar gain control. Today, best suited buildings for GEOTABS and hybridGEOTABS typically have a high thermal mass, high insulation level, a low window to wall ratio but still adequate daylighting and good air tightness. However, in order to lift obstacles for the technology, the ability for the architect to choose other building parameters, which are typically found in our European building stock (larger window area for instance) is also included in the scope of this project.

Since low enthalpy geothermal energy is an efficient and abundant renewable energy source to be found almost everywhere in Europe, it is logical to investigate better design practice and methods to size the system accurately. Therefore, field studies are presented in this report to demonstrate the importance of using EGRT (Enhanced Geothermal Response Test) to verify the actual thermal conductivity along the length of the borehole. This evaluation method enables correct sizing of the Ground Source Heat Exchanger (GSHX) and offers investment cost savings on the borefield up to 15% compared to simulations (e.g. with EED software code) and 7% compared to GRT (geothermal response test), which are the prevailing techniques for installation above 30kW. The current and best practice concerning the design and sizing of heat pumps (including or not the integration of the borefield storage capacity) as well as the ones specifically for the design of TABS are discussed in detail in Chapter 3.

Climate and economical background, political context in relation to national supplies and import of conventional fossil resources are also all very relevant factors to any renewable energy technology uptake. The particularities in some countries are observed in this respect. Today, the biggest and most stable market for GSHP systems is Sweden due to favourable policies. And even if TABS is not the preferred emission system due to climate conditions, some new pilot projects are being completed, with low exergy building solutions in extreme winter

conditions. The heat pump revolution has also taken place in Switzerland, which leads the European market for the number of heat pumps per m². In Spain, shallow geothermal continues experiencing a steady growth and more specifically passive cooling of buildings becomes more and more relevant (for instance space cooling in the residential sector is expected to see a six-fold increase) in order to decrease the carbon intensity of space cooling. Looking at the current situation in Europe we can see many ambitious design concepts which stand at the crossroad of political conditions, rising energy cost, our need to reduce our primary energy consumption and the demand for always higher comfort. The flood of technical solutions and information as well as personal preferences from stakeholders make it particularly difficult to choose an optimal combination of systems. The need for clear and simple guidelines is of uttermost importance. This project will achieve this objective among many others.

In a second part, the report focuses on current and best practise in control engineering techniques of hybridGEOTABS. Current and best practice using Rule Based Controllers (RBC) are discussed. Rule based controllers can be used to guarantee comfort but lead to many inefficiencies in operating these complex building services with several degrees of freedom. Additionally, thermally activated building systems (TABS) increase the thermal mass of buildings. The increased thermal mass due to the TABS and higher required insulation levels increase the thermal time constants of buildings. New buildings are therefore harder to control using rule-based control systems that use control logic such as hysteresis controllers, PI(D)s and heating curves, which do not inherently integrate system delays and forecasts. Moreover, RBC strategies typically do not anticipate the impact of future disturbances on the current control action, or the impact of the current control action on future system states and therefore on the future system control action.

Also badly performing RBCs can lead to long commissioning (and re-commissioning) periods and possibly even to the installation of extra secondary systems. This further increases the total cost of ownership of a building, and can even lead to energy efficient devices being switched off in favour of secondary systems, or a malfunction of the energy-efficient device or the controller may go unnoticed if the secondary device takes over. This is one of the reason why recent developments in Model Predictive Control (MPC) to design but also operate hybridGEOTABS building are implemented in this project and constitute the main research topic of work package 3.

Finally, this report takes a look at the future of low exergy building HVAC systems. Indeed, in outstanding projects making full use of the potential of hybridGEOTABS-MPC concept, the intrinsic storage capacity, available in the building, TABS and underground, combined with the predictive control offered by MPC, offer maximal flexibility to the broader energy systems. This allows to increase the R2ES share even further by using demand side flexibility (either by applying demand response program or using energy storage solutions).

The hybridGEOTABS-MPC concept involves multiple energy vectors: heat/cold, electricity and potentially also (bio) gas or hydrogen in the hybrid part of the concept. This allows to extend the storage options even further by implementing power-to-X, using the appropriate energy vector depending on the demand. Furthermore, interactions between multiple grids (electricity, thermal, natural gas, hydrogen) need to be considered. All these options will contribute to the decarbonisation of heating, cooling and ventilation in buildings.

Table of Contents

Nomenclature	8
Introduction	10
1. Review of current design processes.....	12
1.1. Introduction	12
1.2. Feasibility stage.....	13
1.3. Pre-design stage	15
2. Challenges for the HVAC Designer.....	17
2.1. Integrative design approach.....	17
2.2. Reducing the design costs	17
3. Design Practice.....	18
3.1. Building architectural design aspects.....	18
3.2. Ground Source Heat Exchanger (GSHX) design	19
3.2.1. Current practice: Geothermal Response Test (GRT).....	19
3.2.2. Best practice: Enhanced Geothermal Response Test (EGRT)	20
3.2.3. Comparison of results and cost benefits.....	22
3.2.4. GRT and EGRT equipment and test execution cost	24
3.2.5. Summary.....	25
3.3. Heat pump design and integration	26
3.4. TABS design.....	27
3.4.1. General design principles	27
3.4.2. Simple calculations of load profile	28
3.4.3. Correct TABS and ceiling configuration selection	29
3.4.4. Dynamic simulation of TABS zones and performance	29

3.5.	hybridGEOTABS design variation in Europe	30
3.5.1.	Switzerland	30
3.5.2.	Spain	32
3.5.3.	Scandinavia	37
3.5.4.	Belgium	38
4.	Control Practice.....	40
4.1.	Heat pump control.....	40
4.1.1.	Rule Based Control (RBC)	40
4.1.2.	Bivalent mode operation.....	42
4.2.	hybridGEOTABS building controls - current and best practice	42
4.3.	Model Predictive Control (MPC) recent developments	44
4.3.1.	MPC - White Box Approach (Infracx office)	47
4.3.2.	MPC - Grey Box Approach (Libeznice School)	49
5.	Future Outlook	53
5.1.	Towards a clean energy transition and grid flexibility	53
5.2.	Outstanding practice	55
	Conclusion	56
	Bibliography	57

Nomenclature

RzES	Renewable and Residual Energy Sources
MPC	Model Predictive Control
RBC	Rule Based Control
TABS	Thermally Activated Building Systems
GSHP	Ground Source Heat Pump
GSHX	Ground Source Heat Exchanger
PID	Proportional Integral Derivative
HP	Heat Pump
HVAC	Heating Ventilation and Air Conditioning
GRT	Geothermal Response Test
GFA	Gross Floor Area
EGRT	Enhanced Geothermal Response Test
DTM	Dynamic Thermal Modelling
HDD	Heating Degree Days
CDD	Cooling Degree Days
BRCM	Building Resistance-Capacitance Modelling

hybrid
GEOTABS

Controlling the power of the ground by integration

Introduction

This report on current and good (also called “best”) practice is essential to appreciate fully the benefits of the project outcomes of WP2 and WP3 combined, namely the benefits of having a set of design guidelines and user-friendly, reliable sizing tool for the early stages of design (D2.6 and D2.7) and progress in MPC development.

It should also help the readers, whether they are HVAC designers, architects, design and build construction firms or real estate investors, to understand the current problems related to the design and control of hybrid GEOTABS building systems and at the same time how the new developments in the field of design and control at the heart of this project will enable them to harvest substantial primary energy and cost savings thanks to these new developed solutions. Also, they will be able to eventually break-off with traditional non-efficient design methods.

With some best practice examples showing how the technology is implemented in a commercial project environment and also a discussion on future outlook of hybridGEOTABS-MPC technology for commercial projects, readers will familiarise themselves with the technology in order to propose these systems for commercial residential, office, elderly care home and school projects on the same basis as other more traditional fossil fuel based HVAC options.

The main objectives of this report are to:

- Give an accurate picture of the **current design practice for hybridGEOTABS** in Europe.
- Describe the **main challenges** faced by HVAC designers during early design
- Explain what qualifies as **best practice design for each core modules** of a hybridGEOTABS building: i.e. best GSHX sizing, heat pump (HP) design and integration, thermally activated building system (TABS) design
- Discuss **regional variations** in hybrid GEOTABS design in Europe
- Describe what constitutes best **integrative design methods**
- Discuss current and best practice in **control** of hybrid GEOTABS buildings: pros and cons of each approach, limitation of current control techniques for hybrid GEOTABS
- Give an overview of **the future** design and control **possibilities** with hybrid GEOTABS and their integration with broader sustainability goals (with MPC for example)

One of the goals of this report is to give an honest account of the current and best practices, how often do they occur and where in Europe do they mostly occur. But first it is very important for ease of understanding of this report and further guidebooks, to define what exactly we understand under the different terms:

1. **A GEOTABS building:** a building using geothermal heat and cooling resource in combination with a brine/water heat pump and TABS to deliver heating and cooling to the zone.
2. **A hybridGEOTABS building:** a building using a GEOTABS concept to cover the baseload energy demand (steady, non-fluctuating energy demand) and a secondary energy source and (possibly) emission system to cover the residual energy demand of the building and zones.

3. **Current practice:** refers in our project to GEOTABS or hybrid GEOTABS buildings and systems (i.e. with or without fast reacting secondary emission system and with or without secondary production system) with RBC (using current general design rules) where the RBC is not necessarily properly tuned and most of the time not commissioned properly. The secondary heating/cooling production is based on fossil fuel resources.
4. **Good (or Best) practice** refers to carefully and well-sized hybridGEOTABS building and systems, with RBC development and commissioning according to state-of-the-art rules. It includes some degrees of hybridity next to the geothermal resource on the production side (and if required also on the emission side). It is designed mostly by experienced designers who keep themselves up to date with innovative practice. However, this design is time-consuming and used expensive sizing process involving simulation from the early design stages.
5. **Innovative practice:** “hybridGEOTABS-MPC” systems, using the design methods and MPC control developed in this project.

Points 3 and 4. are referred in this report as “(hybrid)GEOTABS-RBC” while point 5. is called “hybridGEOTABS-MPC”.

The expected outcomes of this report will serve as a ground for different chapters proposed in the final REHVA Guidebook (D7.5: REHVA Guidebook “Design Guidelines for hybridGEOTABS buildings”) and which will be published at the end of this project. This will be a summary of the newly developed and truly innovative design and control methods showing the strength of the project in comparison to what is practice today.

1. Review of current design processes

1.1. Introduction

Task T2.5 of WP2 focuses on the completion of a set of hybridGEOTABS design guidelines and a sizing tool based on the results of a newly developed algorithm, which enables a quick sizing of TABS, heat pump and associated ground source heat exchanger power as well as of the secondary (fast-reacting) systems. The objective is to cut drastically the time and cost involved in preparing a pre-design package of a hybridGEOTABS project in a commercial environment. The design process should be as quick as for any other conventional heating and cooling technology, for example when using rules of thumbs or well-established standards, energy benchmarks and static heat transfer calculations to pre-size conventional HVAC plant items.

Together with a streamlined sizing methodology, which can be used during feasibility and pre-design, the HVAC specialist designer will also have access to a quick evaluation tool to compare the environmental and economic benefits of the proposed hybrid GEOTABS solution against other energy concept variations.

However, in order to capture the needs of the tool's user group (HVAC engineer mainly but also architects, energy consultants) a first assessment of the current design practices is required. The information gathered here is a harmonized view on current design procedures using mainly information from the two design consultancy in this Consortium, namely Boydens Engineering Ltd in Belgium (Flanders) and Lemon Consult AG in Switzerland.

At first it is required to define the "feasibility study" and "pre-design" requirements.

A decision tree from a previous study¹, shown in figure 1.1 below presents design process, which consists of two main parts: a decision tree and a design tree.

In the first phase of the project, a feasibility study will be performed to decide if hybridGEOTABS can be applied. The feasibility study is a preliminary study undertaken in the very early stage of a project. It tends to be carried out when a project is large or complex, or where there is some doubt or controversy regarding the proposed development. The goal of the study is to establish whether the project is viable and to help identify feasible options². The building is studied as one black box system and general assumptions regarding its energy demand and peak load are made, based on typical benchmarks and values from experience. The monetary aspect is decisive at this stage and very often project "costs" are only evaluated from a capital expenditure perspective, omitting the benefits of such low exergy systems in terms of environmental costs, operational and maintenance costs. Data available to perform a feasibility study are very scarce and inaccurate, therefore designers' experience, its company DNA as well as the one from the architecture studio play a very important role in the negotiation with the client.

In case the feasibility study points out that hybridGEOTABS can be applied, because it achieves the objectives (either economic or environmental) of the Client, the second phase can be initiated, starting with the pre-design phase. The pre-design consists of a more detailed exercise compared to the design in the feasibility study in the following aspects:

¹ Towards optimal design and control of geothermal heat pumps combined with thermally activated building systems in offices (2011-2013) – WP2-D2: Decision/design tree for GEO-HP-TABS

² www.designingbuildings.co.uk

- It uses an integrated approach: as an example, in the design of TABS, integration of systems, acoustical measures, lighting and structural aspects must all be considered in parallel.
- The design is based on in-situ ground testing for projects exceeding 30kW. This has an important impact on the systems layout and sizing.
- It uses a slightly more detailed calculation method.

Figure 1.1: Design Processes

In this section we will present the process and estimation methods currently applied during the early design stages to evaluate the feasibility of a hybridGEOTABS building and how designers proceed to draft an initial functioning concept (pre-design).

1.2. Feasibility stage

The use of GEOTABS should be considered at the very beginning of the project in a feasibility study which leads to a simple yes/no decision and a basic energy concept. Compared to GEOTABS buildings, which are subjected to severe restrictions regarding the building and its immediate environment, the hybridGEOTABS concept increases tremendously the applicability and feasibility of the GEOTABS technology (GSHX, heat pump and TABS) since these are complemented with the fast reacting secondary system, making it hybrid and therefore more resilient, removing many existing barriers for the technology to take off.

Therefore, the question that the HVAC designers in general need to ask themselves during feasibility stage is no longer:

“Can I apply GEOTABS to my project?” but rather **“How much GEOTABS can I use on my project?”** in order to offer the project owner a competitive alternative to a conventional building services strategy.

When following this question and discussion on the level of hybridity (2 sources / 2 emissions) required in the concept, designers today usually end up rejecting this option because of the inability to answer the above question. Indeed, the systems must be appropriately sized, at the risk of making the investment costs explode and the building energy systems totally inefficient.

Additional secondary systems must remain affordable in order for the overall HVAC package, despite its numerous environmental benefits, to remain competitive with traditional less expensive (but mostly fossil fuel-based) heating and cooling systems, since the GEOTABS part is on average 20% more expensive in terms of investment cost.

In the following sections, current practice and information available at feasibility and subsequently pre-design stage, have been collected mainly from engineering practice in Switzerland (LC), Belgium (BOY) and Spain (GEOTER).

In Switzerland we found out no significant difference at this stage of the project compared to Belgium or Spain: HVAC engineers usually resort to “rules of thumb” guidelines, basic assumptions, GIS data, simple calculations based on standards, sizing data available from manufacturers, in order to assess the integration of the different hybridGEOTABS components into one working concept. One main difference might be that the engineering consultancy firms in Switzerland usually have a clear mandate to investigate different energy strategies during this phase of the project, while in many other European countries, this work is not always remunerated (part of the acquisition, commercial strategy for the building services firm), which may have an impact on the feasibility study’s outcome.

The data usually available at the start of this early stage are:

1. Client’s Project Brief (also known as Owner’s Project Requirements)
2. Definition of the construction project, elaborated by the architect with rough key data:
 - Building type and function (e.g. light weight residential building with some retail units on ground floor)
 - Gross floor area
 - Basic site and floor plans
 - Number of floors underground/above ground
 - First design narrative
3. Site information: using maps or reports showing what can be found on the plot of land (contaminated land, water streams, sensitive land area etc.), previous engineering studies if available.

Based on very little information, the HVAC engineer and/or energy & sustainability consultant firms produce a report with the following objectives:

- Establish a clear picture of the project, the site and surroundings’ constraint(s)
- Clarify what energy sources are available and which ones make sense for the project in relation to the Client’s brief and architectural project.
- Help identify feasible HVAC options (up to 3-4 variations) in a qualitative assessment. The aim is to display a range of technically feasible, economically viable options for the building and prepare a short list of pro & cons related to life cycle cost, environmental impact (primary energy, CO₂ emission) but also space requirement, flexibility, maintenance issues associated with the proposed concept. This remains a high-level assessment.
- Cost the HVAC package as a whole (only split between HVAC and sanitary installations) with a +/- 20% cost uncertainty.
- Building automation (controls) design and costs are not evaluated at this stage.

The assessment is usually presented in a structured way so the client can see how to proceed to the next stage. Based on this feasibility study, a strong concept usually emerges, outweighing the other options (e.g. geothermal energy in combination with HP, PVT collectors and TABS).

It appears that during this initial phase, straightforward methods are used to assess the applicability of hybridGEOTABS. However, due to the large effect of thermal inertia in TABS heated and/or cooled structure, we understand that the dynamic behaviour of the building coupled with the ground system should be considered at all times. The general standards based on steady-state calculation methods are therefore inadequate. In the detailed design phase, integrated dynamic simulations are needed that include the building, HVAC systems and components, hydraulic circuit, climate, ground, user and the control strategies.

Another issue noticed at this stage is a lack of life cycle costing analysis during feasibility studies, which means most of the time designer only consider the capital investment costs of the HVAC systems without investigating operating and maintenance costs over the entire life cycle of the building. Best practice looks at the overall life cycle costs (LCC) of the building. In this case the Total Cost of Ownership (TCO) is an appropriate metric to use.

1.3. Pre-design stage

The pre-design implements a set of strategic decision from the feasibility stage and uses simplified load calculation and sizing methods (rather on a whole building level) as well as a rough calculation of the energy performance (based on full load hours from norms and benchmarks, rule of thumbs, values from experience, etc.). Current design practices are therefore suboptimal when it comes to the design of hybridGEOTABS and no actual guidelines have been developed to size hybridGEOTABS components and answer these two main questions:

- What is the percentage of load covered by the “GEO-TABS” part of the concept (as opposed to the secondary fast reacting system) required for the concept to meet the project’s requirement?
- Does the ground source storage capacity allow a sustainable (balanced) coverage of a sufficiently large part of the heating and cooling loads of the building, in order for the reduced operational cost to compensate for the currently high investment costs of the borefield?

To answer this optimisation problem with multiple objectives (minimum primary energy consumption and greenhouse gas emissions, life cycle cost) and multiple constraints (thermal comfort range, long term use of the ground, etc.) HVAC designers currently try to solve the problem case by case:

1. Either by applying thermal energy balance steady state calculation on the building envelope and/or one typical room, using sizing methodology for each individual components according to local and/or European standards.

Heating and cooling loads are mainly influenced by the local climate, a few major design aspects, the internal loads profile as well as the needs of the customer (level of indoor environmental quality, thermal comfort band, level of flexibility required etc.). These parameters can be estimated at this stage from experience and/or from building benchmarks. From this input a steady state calculation (building heat transfer balance) to calculate the building peak heating and cooling demand is performed. This is largely insufficient and will lead to oversizing the systems, for 2 reasons, the buffering capacity of the TABS/building thermal mass is ignored and secondly the omission of diversity factors and compensating loads which will lead to lower peaks in energy demand.

2. Or by using Dynamic Thermal Modelling software (DTM), where the entire building and the ground physical properties must be modelled. This entails including thermal inertia of the building mass, and all other factors affecting the building dynamically, and which results most of the time in prohibitive soft engineering costs.

Therefore, in case of a hybridGEOTABS building pre-design (without any simulation study) this may only constitute a very rough starting point for the optimisation procedure of the detailed design phase. The detailed design phase includes the sizing and calculation of performance indicators of the building including its systems and their components, the hydraulic circuit, the ground heat exchanger and the control strategy.

2. Challenges for the HVAC Designer

From current practice, challenges are also identified that prevent the technology to deploy. Key points that must be safeguarded during design are:

- to maintain thermal comfort when sudden and significant changes in heating or cooling loads appear
- to maintain the thermal balance of the ground
- to design and control the system optimally
- to decrease investment, design and commissioning costs

Due to multiple interactions between the different aspects of the concept, it is clear that these key points can only be apprehended with an integrative design approach.

2.1. Integrative design approach

On the one hand the design of a hybridGEOTABS system requires knowledge (data in the form of a load duration curve) or assumptions based on experience on the load distribution in relation to the storage (or buffer) capacity of the building equipped with TABS. And on the other hand it also requires knowledge on how to size the different part of the hybrid systems (GEOTABS core components and secondary fast reacting systems) and integrate them in “good proportion” together with the main GEOTABS systems (geothermal heat exchanger, heat pump and TABS). This integration of a secondary fast-reacting system, often needed to react to a sudden change in heating or cooling demand that cannot be achieved with the inherently sluggish TABS thermal response.

At this point very limited guidelines are available for sizing a hybrid GEOTABS system, which leads in most cases to oversizing the different components (for security reasons on the designer side, should anything go wrong and the building need extra heating or cooling). This leads to higher investment costs as well as lower overall efficiency. The need for an integrative design approach is mandatory in the case of hybridGEOTABS building. Integrative design requires that the people representing each system components keep in close and continuous contact to discover and understand synergies between the systems. This is in reality hardly ever achieved despite some incentives from different green building labels such as LEED, BREEAM or DGNB for rewarding projects showcasing integrative design.

Thanks to the new developed sizing methods resulting from the work completed in WP2 and WP3, a first sizing of all the components will be provided to the HVAC engineer enabling a starting point for the design, which can be further discussed, adapted by the different parties involved in the final concept.

2.2. Reducing the design costs

As mentioned before, the combination of TABS with more flexible heating and cooling emission systems, and the geothermal system with additional heat generation systems, increases the applicability and feasibility of the concept. However, the design and control of the system becomes more difficult. The REHVA Guidebook no. 20 mentions hybrid generation systems for TABS and several research projects clarify the problem. However, no generally accepted guidelines have been developed for the particular design conditions for the sizing and integration of secondary systems. This not only leads to further increase of the investment costs, but also to excessive engineering and commissioning costs, since the sizing and control of the system requires case-by-case simulation work and extensive commissioning work.

3. Design Practice

3.1. Building architectural design aspects

The following aspects, influenced mainly by the architectural concept must be consider in order to create the best “hosting” environment and a good starting point for the successful integration of hybridGEOTABS energy systems in the architectural project:

Geothermal heat pumps combined with thermally activated building systems cannot be applied in all climate types and internal heat gains conditions without the support of a secondary fast reacting system. However, the dedicated share of “GEO-TABS” (and therefore renewable energy) can be optimised thanks to best sustainable design practice.

A “bioclimatic” or “environmental” approach is a good first attempt. It bases the choices of building shape, site, orientation and spatial layout on the particular features of the site (climate, dominant wind direction, soil characteristics, solar exposure).

The building designer should also aim at minimising the peaks of the heating and cooling loads by reducing internal heat gains, providing adequate solar gain control and while also reducing the ventilation and transmission heat losses. Generally, all suitable buildings have a high insulation level, a low window to wall ratio and good air tightness.

Special attention at project inception should be paid to the following sustainable design points:

➤ **Building Compactness**

Building volumes should be as compact as possible. By keeping a low ratio between the thermal envelope area A_{th} (in contact with the outside air and also with the ground and unheated rooms) and the Gross Floor Area (“ A_{th} ” / GFA) a very compact form is achieved. This ratio should in any case remain below 1.0 and ideally below 0.8. Building compactness is the most important factor in design of low energy buildings.

➤ **High insulation and airtightness level**

A compact building design should be combined with good level of insulation for the walls and roofs for high performance: in Switzerland, Germany and Scandinavia, U-Values <0.13 for a roof and <0.15 for walls with insulation thicknesses of 200-220 mm are extremely common for new buildings. Thermal bridges (or cold bridges) which can account for a large part of the heat losses in building should be avoided by careful detailing of the connection between the outside walls, floor, roof and windows. Special care must be taken on the connection of balcony or external circulation structure to the main building structure. They should be disconnected if possible.

Air infiltration through the building envelope resulting in poor energy efficiency, draught and increased discomfort can with today’s material be avoided at low cost. The use of adaptive vapour proof (damp proofing) membranes that have a lower air permeability in winter and higher one in summer, as well as air tight adhesive sealants is common knowledge.

➤ **Thermal inertia using the building mass** (heavy weight building)

Solid concrete or masonry elements should work as a reservoir in a low exergy TABS operated building. For this principle to work, it is very important not to cover the exposed concrete surface (ceilings and/or floors

but internal walls can also be used), so that the heat transfer can actually take place between the activated concrete mass and the room air mass. The thermal mass of a building is therefore crucial for the operation of TABS. If the activated mass is too low, the system is unable to perform as desired and the room temperatures might drift out of the acceptable comfort range.

- **Windows-to-wall ratio and solar protection** (control of solar heat gains vs. optimisation of daylight)
In temperate climate, a good percentage of glazed area in relation to the external wall is situated somewhere between 40% and 50% on the south side of the building and between 15% to 25% on the north side. However, depending on the heat and cooling demand profile specific to the building typology or users, this must be analysed carefully. Today high performance glazing allows the utilisation of solar gains in winter while protecting the internal space from overheating in summer. Additionally, to the controlled glass performance, it is important to first implement external shading elements, either by the use of canopies, external weather controlled blinds, external window louvres and planting (tree canopy, green roof and facade).

Typically, fully glazed office high rise building do not meet the criteria of a TABS operated building. Although not recommended, latest progress in high performance glazing as well as new smart façade such as an electrochromic glass can push these limits. Furthermore, hybridGEOTABS buildings, thanks to the hybrid secondary fast reacting system can also cope with sudden change in loads and can accommodate a large range of building façade design, allowing (within limits) the architect more design freedom.

- **Integration of night time natural ventilation** (night time purge or re-cooling)
Natural ventilation strategy and more specifically night time flushing of the slab is certainly a very important best practice in building with high thermal mass in summer. It can be implemented for instance with a glazed atrium concept connected to the office spaces and opening the windows onto this central atrium at night (so called chimney effect).

Design of building and plant systems is too often focusing on specific low energy features, losing sight of overall performance. The designer should therefore be aware of the integral design process in which all performance aspects are addressed in search of overall building quality.

3.2. Ground Source Heat Exchanger (GSHX) design

3.2.1. Current practice: Geothermal Response Test (GRT)

When it comes to sizing the geothermal borehole field, the use of a GRT (Geothermal Response Test) is the most prevalent practice in Europe. It consists of an on-site test to determine the thermodynamic parameters of the subsoil. Besides, for installations above 30 kW it is common and recommended to perform a pilot borehole in accordance with VDI 4640 standard (VDI-Standard: VDI 4640 Blatt 2. Thermal use of the underground - Ground source heat pump systems). Borehole used for a GRT can be used afterwards as a geothermal exchanger.

A GRT is used for practical comparison of theoretical data since performing such test allows us to know the effective thermal conductivity (describes the heat transfer through conductivity in the subsoil) and the thermal resistance of the probe (indicates what should be the thermal resistance between the collector circuit and the subsoil for dissipation of power), with the aim to optimise the system and size a field of geothermal probes. Also,

when comparing the GRT with a soil samples analysis completed in a laboratory, it is observed that the measurements made of undisturbed soil conditions are not comparable with those affected by factors found in usual geothermal probe conditions like filling material, technical quality of the probe, its installation process thus as the effect of the phreatic level.

The process of a GRT is as follow:

- (1) Before the GRT is started, the undisturbed ground temperature must be determined. This can be measured by measuring the temperature of circulated water through the borehole without heating over 20 minutes. This is allowing enough time to see the temperature stabilised. In order to do so, a heat transfer fluid is circulated at a certain velocity with the aim of filling the probe circuit 1.5 times. The mean fluid temperature corresponds to the undisturbed mean temperature along the borehole.
- (2) After this initial 20-minute-long measurement, the next step is to switch on the heater and the monitoring system. During the test, the heat transfers into the ground surrounding the borehole is essentially radial and relatively constant along the borehole. The 36 to 48 hours' test starts and the heat transfer fluid is gradually warmed up making it circulate through immersion heaters. Temperature data are provided by two temperature sensors at the top of the borehole and power applied is controlled and collected during the process. Hence, the average thermal conductivity can be obtained.

Practical example:

A GRT was performed in one of the case studies of hybridGEOTABS project in Spain (Gijón, Spain) from the 20th to the 23th of March 2018. The nature of the ground in this place is dominated by limestones, loams, clays and sandstones. The borehole was drilled using a direct mud rotary drilling method to achieve the introduction of the geothermal probe with a diameter of 40 mm to the depth of 124 meters, and backfill material with outstanding thermal conductivity was used to fill the borehole.

The average thermal conductivity obtained was 2.91 W/(m·K).

3.2.2. Best practice: Enhanced Geothermal Response Test (EGRT)

In hybridGEOTABS project, significant improvements in this process have been achieved, by executing more developed, upgraded and detailed GRTs than usual. In a traditional GRT, only flow and return temperatures at the top of the borehole are measured, while an EGRT (Enhanced Geothermal Response Test) enable us to obtain a temperature profile at all the levels of the borehole, measuring accurately how the temperature changes with depth as a function of the flow and the thermal stress of the borehole. The interpretation of the results of an EGRT allows to calculate the effective thermal conductivity and the thermal resistance of the boreholes along the depth of the geothermal probe, centimetre per centimetre. With this data it is possible to find where the optimal areas of the sub-soil are and, even, to know the influence of the different materials or groundwater in the case that these exists.

Practical example

An EGRT was performed in the same borehole presented in the above example and it was based on a 12-hour undisturbed ground temperature test, a 48-hour heating test and a 48-hour of temperature recovery test. To make a difference with respect to the traditional GRT, ten different sensors were running all along the length of

the geothermal probe while a 130-meter-long heating element were heating the heat transfer fluid. During the EGRT, temperature of the ground was obtained, depending on the depth during the heating-controlled process. Results can be consulted below. In figure 3.1, the equipment used is shown.

Figure 3.1. EGRT equipment

In figure 3.2, temperature profiles during the undisturbed and heating process are shown. Red curve validates the typical theoretical depth-temperature unaltered profile of the Earth. The rest of colours represent temperatures along the borehole length, which have been represented in different times to verify the temperature changes while a constant heat is injected. With all this information, conductivity along the borehole is known and the optimal depth of the boreholes can be calculated considering the thermal loads of the building which we want to provide heating/cooling and domestic hot water, achieving the length where there is the highest average conductivity, all in ranges that allow to satisfy building demands. Thermal conductivity differences are explained by the different hydrogeological conditions.

Figure 3.2. Temperature profile during EGRT execution.

In figure 3.3, conductivity data obtained along the borehole test is shown. The average thermal conductivity is 2.91 W/(m·K), obviously the same value which was calculated during the GRT performed. Higher values are obtained due to the existence of an aquifer with an important water flow. This is especially reflected between depths between 65 and 85 meters, where the data obtained in test is so high that it isn't even coherent to provide a numerical value for this thermal conductivity. It's considered that the flow of water from this area is much more considerable than at 28, 36- and 118-meters depth. Similarly, the lower value obtained is approximately 1.25 W/(m·K), obtained at 55 meters of depth.

Performing a borehole field simulation, EGRT allows to calculate the optimum depth of the boreholes depending on the thermal loads of the building.

Figure 3.3 Effective thermal conductivity along the depth.

3.2.3. Comparison of results and cost benefits

Subsequently, three different simulations were carried out with EED (Earth Energy Designer) software to show the importance of knowing the conductivity along the borehole. In all of them VDI 4640 Guideline has been considered.

1. Simulations performed by engineering, when the conductivity is estimated based on geological and hydrogeological bibliographic studies as well as on the experience.
2. Simulations performed after performing a GRT, when average thermal conductivity is known.

3. Simulations performed after performing an EGRT, when thermal conductivity is known throughout the depth.

The required heat exchanger is longer when conductivity has been obtained from engineering than when has been determined by the GRT, due to the oversizing that used to be done for the estimation of conductivity. Similarly, the required exchanger length is higher when conductivity has been obtained from GRT than when it has been determined by the EGRT because it is possible to optimize the length of the boreholes and finally the total meters to drill for the borehole field are lower.

After EGRTs executed during the project, we can affirm that pre-engineering sizing has a reduction of 4-10% of investment in the borehole field performing a GRT and a reduction of 14-16% performing an EGRT. That means, an EGRT has meant a 7% investment reduction compared to the GRT.

In figure 3.4, in this particular case in Gijón, conductivities obtained in three simulations are shown, as well as total drilling length necessary according each sizing. On figure 3.2.3, costs are represented, being smaller in EGRT case study after obtaining more conductivity.

Figure 3.4. Average conductivity, total drilling length and costs in Gijón (case studies: Engineering, GRT, EGRT)

Through an EGRT, areas of high conductivity have been found along the depth, and together with the study through EED software has allowed the optimization of the global geothermal system. Performing an EGRT is possible to analyse the complete information about the subsoil and decide the best solution considering all the project conditions, always optimizing the number of meters to drill. EGRT obtains savings in investment costs

enhancing the sizing of the borehole field, increasing the security of supply and the optimum functioning of the HVAC installation.

3.2.4. GRT and EGRT equipment and test execution cost

An economic comparative for an EGRT execution (monitoring systems that measure subsoil parameters throughout all the length of the borehole) versus a GRT execution (monitoring systems that calculate the average of subsoil parameters) is shown in this section.

First, EGRT equipment costs and GRT equipment costs will be analysed.

Table 3.1 GRT and EGRT equipment cost

Component description	Unit	GRT component cost (€)	EGRT component cost (€)
Data acquirer (e.g. Nanodac Schneider):	1	1.305,00	X
Temperature & pressure spheric sensor meters (e.g. Enoware pig)	5	X	3.675,00
Circulation pump (e.g. Wilo 25/1-8):	1	347,00	347,00
Three-phase electric power meter (e.g. SCEALL2UPUL80):	1	239,00	239,00
Flowmeter with two temperature sensors (e.g. Watts Superstatic 440	1	509,00	X
Electric resistance (e.g. Stiebel Eltron BGC/45)	2	494,00	X
Heating Cable 130 meters (e.g. Solutrace XPI-50-F)	1	X	1.944,00
Material (accessories and piping elements)	1	250,00	120,00
Box where hydraulics elements are located (e.g. ZARGES K470	1	387,00	387,00
Labour cost of equipment's assembly and programming	1	1.200,00	900,00
Total		4.731,00 €	7.612,00 €

Total cost GRT equipment is 4.731,00 € and total cost EGRT equipment is 7.612,00 €. It is concluded that EGRT equipment is 60% more expensive than GRT equipment.

It should be note that using EGRT instead of GRT has resulted in cost savings around 3.000–6.000 € in any of the previous projects analysed in Spain because of savings of meters to drill. Therefore, despite the difference between the manufacturing cost, EGRT equipment allows immediate payback in the first project. And both,

EGRT and GRT, are portable test devices to be used in different projects during their useful life (around 10 years). To conclude, different of cost of EGRT and GRT equipment is not significant.

Secondly, the costs of running the tests in the two cases will be explained.

The borehole execution and testing process are exactly the same whether using a GRT or an EGRT. Same needs of water, electricity power and demand and test duration. Therefore, the costs of GRT and EGRT execution are the same. Next, a standard budget for GRT or EGRT test execution is detailed.

Table 3.2. Cost GRT and EGRT test execution

Task	Unit	GRT Cost (€) Average data	EGRT cost (€) Data along the drilling
Drilling execution (one borehole 127m depth)	127 m	4.290,06	4.290,06
High conductivity mortar	2,8 t	577,50	577,50
Geothermal probe and auxiliary equipment	1 unit	585,43	585,43
Drilling mud collection and management	1 unit	490,63	490,63
Drilling machine transport	1 unit	1.300,00	1.300,00
Test costs (water, electricity)	1 unit	625,00	625,00
Report (technician and engineer labour)	1 unit	850,00	850,00
Total		8.718,62 €	8.718,62 €

To conclude, the total cost for borehole drilling and testing for a GRT and EGRT process is the same, amounting to ca. 8.700 €.

3.2.5. Summary

Since low enthalpy geothermal energy (also called “shallow geothermal application” at depths less than 400 m) is an efficient and abundant renewable energy that can be found almost everywhere in the world, it is logical to investigate better methods to size the system accurately. Field studies were carried out within this project to verify the importance of the conductivity calculation along a geothermal borehole for its correct sizing and economic advantages it offers in this project.

With the conductivities obtained with an EGRT and simulations carried out with EED software, the optimal configuration of the geothermal boreholes can be decided. The EGRT allows the design team to make an informed decision on the length of each necessary borehole and reduce the need for unnecessary meters of drilling, therefore reducing the total investment cost of the geothermal installation...

A cost analysis of GRT and EGRT equipment and test has been carried out, taking into account both the elements that contain the equipment and the labour cost required to manufacture them. It is concluded that EGRT

equipment is 60% more expensive than GRT but test process is the same (technically and economically) in both cases.

However, it must be noted that EGRT gives more information for sizing a geothermal field than GRT. This detailed information has resulted (please see Deliverable 6.2) in cost savings around 3.000–6.000 € in any of the projects analysed in Spain because of savings of total meters to drill. Therefore, despite the difference between the manufacturing cost, EGRT equipment allows immediate payback in the first project. And both, EGRT and GRT, are portable test devices to be used in different projects during their useful life (around 10 years). To conclude, different of cost of EGRT and GRT equipment is not significant.

3.3. Heat pump design and integration

Current design uses general guidelines where the thermal power of the heat pump is chosen in function of the heat load of the building. These guidelines are described in EN 12831.

In typical system configurations, the heat output of the heat pump is set to approx. 50 to 70% of the maximum required heating load in bivalent parallel modus (curve A on figure 3.5). In this modus, the heat pump is used to deliver the maximum energy output to the building. Only when the heat pump power is not high enough to deliver the actual heat load of the building, the missing power is added by a secondary heating system in accordance with EN 12831 of the building. The share of the heat pump in the annual heating work is approx. 85 to 92 %. Depending on the outside temperature and the heat load, the heat pump control switches on the 2nd heating system.

- Ⓐ Dual-mode parallel operation
- Ⓑ Dual-mode alternative operation

Figure 3.5. dual mode heat pump operation

If the share of the heat pump is less important or there are external limits to the installation (available electric power, amount of geothermal drillings, thermal conductivity of the ground, ...) the heat pump controller can be switched to bivalent-alternative modus. In this modus, the heat pump controller switches 100% from the heat pump working to the alternative heating system.

A second design method for ground source heat pumps has been proposed in scientific literature (Retkowski and Thöming, 2014; Robert and Gosselin, 2013). In these works, borehole heat exchangers number, depth and spacing, together with GSHP unit capacity, are optimized according to their impact on final operative performances.

A more detailed design method is described in (Conti, 2015 [reference paper](#)). This method is based on the evaluation of energy exchange and performance during the entire operational life. The design method incorporates all the interactions between the building thermal energy loads, the efficiencies of generators (heat pump and back-up systems), and thermal response of the ground on the global energy balance of the ground source heat pump.

The following steps are described into more detail for practical application

1. Calculate heating and cooling needs of the building;
2. Determine ground thermal properties;
3. Decide GSHX configuration and evaluate corresponding heat transfer performance;
4. Provide first guess of boreholes' number, depth and spacing using traditional design methods (e.g. ASHRAE)
5. Create set of possible GHP unit alternatives;
6. Create corresponding set of back-up generators;
7. Perform sensitivity analysis

3.4. TABS design

3.4.1. General design principles

TABS is considered as one of the innovative heating and cooling solutions which has a great potential to benefit energy supply systems in newly built, such as heat pumps. TABS is a type of low-temperature heating and high-temperature cooling system, that follows the general design rules of radiant heating and cooling terminal units in buildings. TABS works in a temperature range that is close to room temperature, therefore, the supply temperatures are usually in the range of following:

- Heating mode: 24 °C – 28 °C
- Cooling mode: 16 °C – 22 °C

The current TABS is commonly designed together with the heating/cooling sources, in terms of different types of heat pumps. Given the temperature range, ground source heat pumps have been a commonly option. Figure 3.6 shows the systematic principle of TABS system design.

Fig. 3.6 TABS design schematics with heating and cooling sources

In terms of conventional cooling sources, supply temperatures of 16 °C are adequate and cost-effective for cooling the heat (latent heat is not cooled by TABS). Chillers (supplying temperatures of 6 °C) are only recommended if additional dehumidification methods are applied. Depending on the size of the system, it is also possible to use separate chillers for dehumidification (approx. 6 °C) and cooling (> 16 °C). An alternative is dehumidification based on sorption.

3.4.2. Simple calculations of load profile

TABS are used primarily for base heating and sensible cooling. Peak heating loads and latent cooling are commonly not covered by TABS. By the defined TABS system, it is important to have a quick heating and cooling profile of the respective building in order to balance the heating/cooling demand of the buildings and the outputs from TABS. The calculation follows the parametric tables. Table 3.3 presents a typical (best practice) design parameters for TABS simple load profile calculation:

Cooling	Heating
1. Supply temperature: 16 °C	1. Supply temperature: 28 °C
2. Return temperature: 20 °C	2. Room temperature: 22 °C
3. Room temperature: 26 °C	3. Heat transfer coefficient:
4. Relative humidity: 50 %	Concrete floor: 10.8 W/m ² K
5. Heat transfer coefficient:	Concrete ceiling: 6 W/m ² K
Concrete floor: 7 W/m ² K	
Concrete ceiling: 10.8 W/m ² K	

Table 3.3 Key parameters to the load profile of TABS

The default piping system uses PE-Xa 20, with pipe space of 150 mm. The calculation method follows the ISO 11855. The best practice of TABS load profile is to reach the supply temperature as close as the room temperature, with a temperature differences between supply and return of 2-5 K. The required water mass flow is calculated by the maximum output (40-60 W/m²) of TABS. The maximum length of the cooling/heating circuit is calculated by the maximum acceptable pressure loss.

In practical experiences, new buildings such as passive houses / net zero buildings have a very low heating or cooling demand. Therefore, the hydraulic design should take into consideration a turbulent mass flow with a Reynolds number above 2300. This may lead to a need for smaller pipe dimension, longer pipe loops or a lower mean water temperature in the early design stage.

3.4.3. Correct TABS and ceiling configuration selection

When the load profile is briefly estimated, the correct ceiling configurations should be determined and corresponding TABS types should be selected, which further leads to different heating/cooling outputs of TABS. In general, TABS works with all types of ceiling configurations, however, suspended ceilings are not suitable for TABS application. The table below summarizes the suitable ceiling configurations:

Ceiling configurations	Suitability
1. Concrete slabs with only a thin floor covering or bonded screed	Yes
2. Concrete slabs with sound insulations	Acceptable, but mostly suitable only suitable for cooling
3. Concrete slabs with raised floors	Acceptable, but mostly suitable only suitable for cooling
4. Concrete slabs with hollow floors	Inspection openings have to be used for the underfloor installations
5. Concrete slabs with suspended ceilings	Not suitable

Table 3.4 Ceiling configurations and their suitability to TABS

When ceiling configurations are determined, the correct TABS heating/cooling outputs should be estimated based on the structures/layers of concrete slabs. The summary of the outputs can found in this table:

TABS without insulation	TABS with sound insulation	TABS with raised floor
Cooling: 57 W/m ²	Cooling: 47 W/m ²	Cooling: 47 W/m ²
Heating: 40 W/m ²	Heating: 29 W/m ²	Heating: 29 W/m ²

Table 3.5. Heating/cooling outputs of TABS based on ceiling configurations

3.4.4. Dynamic simulation of TABS zones and performance

In the last stage, it is commonly necessary to perform dynamic simulation of TABS thermal performance, as well as design the supplementary system. It should be highlighted that dynamic simulation of TABS should be based on multi-zone thermal simulation, due to the fact that TABS is constructed in buildings as a zone-to-zone basis.

There are commercially available software packages to simulate TABS dynamic simulation, such as TRNSYS 15 and beyond.

TABS will not be able to fully dissipate loads at all times. Diurnal temperatures will therefore vary depending on the available thermal mass and actual cooling loads (or base heating loads). To estimate these fluctuations, the variation of loads and their dissipation over time must be considered as a priority in the simulation. There are certain rules of thumbs that should be applied when performing dynamic simulations:

- TABS is sensitive to the radiations. Floor-to-ceiling glazing areas should be carefully considered, as well as the shading impacts. For areas exposed to high solar radiations, high-performance TABS (pipes embedded near the surface) should be considered as an option
- For buildings with high thermal mass, such as façade with double-skin masonry walls, the thermal response time should be assessed. Due to the higher thermal, compared with the buildings with low thermal mass, they are less sensitive to internal and exterior loads. On the other hand, it will lead to also longer thermal response time and peak load supply. It is essential to design the supplementary system based on these characteristics of the buildings
- Place the raisers and respective manifolds in the efficient and cost-effective way

In summary, simulation is always recommended for buildings with large load fluctuations, potentially high moisture load and exposed room locations and need optimizations for secondary systems. However, simulation is not necessarily required for all buildings with TABS in the mild climate when cooling can be fully covered by TABS.

3.5. hybridGEOTABS design variation in Europe

The construction sector counts for nearly 10% of the EU GDP and is its largest single economic activity. Given its role in the achievement of some of the critical climate, environmental and energy-related objectives, the competitiveness of this sector is a permanent political priority. Removing the obstacles arising from different national practices, whether economic but also cultural, is also important for a broader adoption of the hybridGEOTABS concept.

Climatic and geological conditions throughout Europe are varying widely. Also economic background, political willingness of each nation towards reaching EU's energy transition targets as well as construction methods are rather different throughout the 28 EU countries. In this section we try to explore some of the climate specificities and economic reasons which might hinder the deployment of the concept but also some examples of positive market or financial incentives introduced in some European regions, where SME or industrial partners of the consortium are based.

3.5.1. Switzerland

Heating and cooling demands of buildings in a climate changing environment

Detailed studies of long term temperature records show that temperatures in Switzerland rose by around 1.3 K during the 20th century, approximately twice as fast as mean global temperature, with most of the increase occurring in the last three decades. This trend towards higher temperatures is expected to continue, and is expected to lead to a reduction in the need for heating in winter and increased need for cooling in summer. A temperature increase of 1K in winter and 2K in summer reduces heating degree-days (HDD) by about 10% for most locations in Europe. For cooling degree-days (CDD), the change is much more dramatic but in relative

terms. Increases in CDD are likely both to cause an increase in both energies use in buildings that already have cooling and in the fraction of total floor area that has mechanical cooling. For Switzerland, heating accounts for vastly greater energy use and CO₂ emissions than cooling, as it does throughout most of European regions. Consequently, the effect of large percentage increases in cooling demand can be outweighed by much smaller percentage changes in heating demand. Policy measures to reduce cooling energy demand may aim both at reducing the number of installations and at reducing energy use in buildings that have cooling capacity installed. This avoidance strategy will remain viable, however, for the northerly maritime areas (including Ireland, the UK and Scandinavia). While the climate in Switzerland is dominated by heating requirements (HDD = 3200 dd, CDD = 190 dd), new policies are focusing on reducing peak cooling loads in summer as well as reducing the CO₂ intensity of the cooling energy supply to buildings. Passive measures and free cooling strategies via borefield offered by the hybridGEOTABS concept constitute the perfect answers to meeting these objectives.

Trend in heating and cooling systems

For many years now geothermal probes and heat pumps have provided an effective alternative to gas or oil for heating buildings in Switzerland. Germany and Switzerland are the frontrunners in this field. Using other heat sources such as air or waste heat is more recent. However, despite their success, the sales of geothermal probes have stagnated in the last couple of years. This is due to the diversification of the market for renewable energy solutions used in commercial and residential projects, for instance with the recent uptake of ASHP (air source heat pumps) but also in densely populated cities (for instance in Zürich) this could be due the additional studies required to assess the interference of multiple probes in close proximity. Active regeneration is becoming more and more important as the effects of the interactions of the probes are beginning to emerge. Legislation in Switzerland is following this issue closely and an obligation for seasonal borefield regeneration may come soon into effect.

Figure 3.7 Over 5000 geothermal probes exist in the city of Zurich.

Solar panels (photovoltaic mainly) still represent the most visible symbol for renewable energy in buildings in Switzerland and southern Germany. Combined with geothermal heat pump solutions both can have a big impact on reducing CO₂ emissions from buildings. The Swiss Federal Office of Energy predicts that 400,000 heat pumps will be in use by 2020. In the case of new development, heat pump using geothermal energy as a source and sink and/or solar energy is the preferred option from designers across the country.

The air source heat pump market normally dominant in Mediterranean countries is growing very rapidly in Switzerland benefiting from higher efficiency than in the past. They can be installed at a lower investment cost (with no ground work required) and are therefore very competitive on the both new construction and renovation markets (in areas where noise emission level is not an issue).

Energy supply and economic background

Switzerland political forces have embraced the clean energy transition challenge and policies are going in the right direction sending a clear and positive message to investors and to the renewable energy sector in general. The country has taken bold decisions to gradually phase out nuclear power and to reduce by a fifth its greenhouse gas emissions by 2020 with domestic measures only. Switzerland does not produce any fossil fuels and relies heavily on hydro-electricity and imported nuclear power to meet its electricity needs. Energy imports account for about 70% of the country's total primary energy supply. Oil is by far the largest contributor (40%), followed by nuclear power (26%), hydro-electric power (13%), and natural gas (11%). The rest is supplied by renewable sources of energy such as solar, wind, and combustible waste (district heating). The importance of hydro-electric power in the total energy mix owes much to Switzerland's mountainous geography. Retail prices for electricity have been increasing for the past several years. They vary strongly according to supply area. For households, average prices between cantons vary by more than 50%. Within individual cantons, price differences can be even wider, mainly because some mountain municipalities benefit from local low-cost hydropower. For industry, price differences are smaller, but still represent tens of percentage points. Overall electricity price still remains lower than in other countries (around 0.16€ per kWh). Self-production of solar electricity is encouraged with different financial incentives which varies for each canton.

Synergies between heat pump technologies on the demand side and decarbonisation on the supply side, could significantly contribute in achieving the low carbon energy challenge. The biggest threat for the non-deployment of the hybridGEOTABS concept in Europe remains the price ratio between alternative energy sources and electricity. In Switzerland compared to other EU countries, this obstacle is more or less overcome.

3.5.2. Spain

Heating and cooling

Below is an analysis of heating and cooling in Spain in 2015 as well as two future scenarios for 2050, called "Conventionally Decarbonised Scenario" and "Heat Roadmap Europe Scenario for 2050", which have been obtained from the Heat Roadmap Spain ³.

According to this study, heating and cooling are the largest energy demands in Spain, comprising 41% of Spain's final energy demand. This is slightly lower than most European countries, where the average is around 50%. Process heating representing the largest demand. Around a third of the energy is used for space **heating** of buildings, which is atypical compared to most European countries, where space heating generally dominates the end-use. **Cooling**, both process and space cooling, currently amounts to less than 10% of the heating and cooling demand, and while this is on the higher end compared to other European countries, as such it doesn't represent a very large part of the sector or energy system. However, it is also the sector with the greatest variability looking towards the future. In 2015, the following distribution of the total final energy demand was found in Spain:

³ Project H2020 "Heat Roadmap Europe: Building the knowledge, skills, and capacity required to enable new policies and encourage new investments in the heating and cooling sector"

Figure 3.8 Heating and cooling demand in Spain by end-use compared to total final energy demand (2015 values)

Heating

In the Heat Roadmap scenario, compared to 2015, there is a reduction in the amount of individual heater that is required, and an almost full replacement of the individual boilers, which are currently mostly fuelled by gas. In the Conventionally Decarbonised scenario there is an increase of individual heat pumps provided and a decrease of boilers and electric heating, and also generally the total amount of individual heat production decreases.

Figure 3.9 Heat sources for individual heat production in Spain for three scenarios ("Baseline 2015, BL 2015", "Conventionally Decarbonised Scenario 2050, CD 2050" and "Heat Roadmap Europe Scenario for 2050, HRE 2050")

The heat pumps considered are primarily ground-source heat pumps, air-to-air heat pumps, and air-to-water heat pumps with a high level of efficiency and the ability to produce both space heating and hot water with a high COP.

Cooling

Cooling, which is mostly demanded by the industry and service sector, is considered in the forecast scenarios in a similar way as heating. However, the cooling sector is more diverse than the heating sector, and the spatial analysis and energy system modelling that lead to this result are not as methodologically robust as those for the heating market.

The individual cooling demand is mostly supplied using split units, large split units, and chillers of varying sizes. Cooling is one of the fastest growing of the thermal sectors, but supply options can be highly efficient, with COPs ambitiously expected to be around 6,6 in 2050.

In the case of heating degree days, Spain has much less heating degree days than the EU average, as shown in the following table. Specifically, the EU has 2'938 HDD while Spain has 1'799 HDD, both in 2018, 63% less. Its evolution has not been significant over the years, so it can be expected to remain constant.

	2009	2010	2011	2012	2013	2014	2015	2016	2017	2018
European Union - 28 countries	3,103.89	3,485.19	2,952.94	3,227.20	3,156.79	2,808.67	2,907.89	3,024.59	3,031.66	2,938.13
Belgium	2,690.22	3,190.26	2,380.51	2,771.38	3,022.16	2,314.58	2,630.21	2,688.91	2,580.04	2,513.90
Bulgaria	2,438.77	2,520.70	2,796.35	2,611.82	2,414.14	2,370.82	2,377.04	2,426.53	2,532.62	2,357.93
Czechia	3,332.83	3,830.85	3,235.75	3,399.50	3,512.39	2,917.71	3,091.85	3,247.27	3,310.47	2,996.42
Denmark	3,235.75	3,978.30	3,150.67	3,413.39	3,397.94	2,850.87	3,113.48	3,136.44	3,117.46	3,051.11
Germany (until 1990 former territories)	3,080.55	3,630.34	2,872.46	3,130.16	3,287.97	2,660.86	2,908.87	3,005.03	2,964.25	2,775.78
Estonia	4,318.40	4,884.30	4,081.92	4,576.28	4,151.99	4,141.95	3,791.22	4,208.15	4,208.16	4,064.73
Ireland	2,811.19	3,168.56	2,764.00	2,862.89	2,835.70	2,630.44	2,912.95	2,746.32	2,670.21	2,756.01
Greece	1,515.34	1,409.89	1,806.95	1,664.76	1,450.99	1,408.34	1,577.85	1,463.71	1,657.68	1,382.68
Spain	1,734.43	1,945.45	1,562.94	1,863.22	1,907.18	1,566.49	1,639.98	1,729.21	1,597.89	1,799.68
France	2,389.49	2,760.53	2,051.14	2,444.31	2,630.56	2,084.82	2,257.97	2,397.83	2,337.95	2,183.55
Croatia	2,279.04	2,529.10	2,370.43	2,363.75	2,301.17	1,894.49	2,250.30	2,272.64	2,330.55	2,148.18
Italy	1,941.73	2,070.15	1,863.53	1,953.67	1,939.70	1,634.60	1,809.52	1,762.23	1,878.20	1,753.68
Cyprus	705.33	495.59	793.93	818.53	700.74	521.50	739.77	680.48	720.73	476.88
Latvia	4,147.58	4,633.10	3,940.24	4,314.39	4,037.15	3,946.65	3,695.33	4,002.70	4,016.22	3,890.73
Lithuania	3,948.96	4,414.32	3,765.26	4,077.33	3,871.80	3,726.64	3,523.31	3,826.89	3,830.39	3,696.08
Luxembourg	2,880.73	3,360.40	2,568.21	2,935.05	3,209.67	2,499.53	2,848.52	2,967.47	2,869.50	2,669.56
Hungary	2,618.08	2,950.78	2,813.70	2,746.34	2,687.02	2,271.83	2,593.27	2,706.57	2,742.05	2,471.63
Malta	533.74	402.81	548.59	662.00	460.49	374.43	541.82	322.12	485.17	366.13
Netherlands	2,727.29	3,311.69	2,516.31	2,814.56	3,010.25	2,284.96	2,624.19	2,680.27	2,544.05	2,526.77
Austria	3,511.11	3,907.07	3,393.86	3,547.05	3,640.03	3,124.73	3,321.63	3,419.01	3,503.32	3,196.45
Poland	3,449.20	3,920.08	3,315.21	3,550.24	3,504.41	3,094.68	3,112.99	3,286.46	3,290.02	3,125.38
Portugal	1,151.28	1,293.97	1,092.56	1,347.63	1,339.36	1,146.46	1,075.56	1,237.10	1,054.56	1,304.61
Romania	2,846.32	3,052.40	3,170.13	3,087.45	2,863.20	2,728.42	2,786.09	2,918.60	2,916.49	2,749.08
Slovenia	2,778.71	3,134.78	2,821.20	2,833.02	2,866.68	2,342.04	2,699.50	2,756.94	2,832.81	2,583.75
Slovakia	3,182.44	3,491.74	3,249.56	3,293.74	3,240.54	2,717.97	3,055.99	3,171.86	3,280.35	2,922.03
Finland	5,619.86	6,190.94	5,233.56	5,855.40	5,274.05	5,244.71	5,032.28	5,337.55	5,524.31	5,363.53
Sweden	5,324.10	6,003.16	4,928.98	5,502.27	5,183.82	4,887.44	4,911.42	5,125.08	5,219.85	5,162.81
United Kingdom	3,020.03	3,452.49	2,836.31	3,181.23	3,179.12	2,739.93	3,014.61	2,976.36	2,864.79	2,936.31

Table 3.6 Heating Degree Days per EU Countries (2009-2018)

The situation is completely opposite in cooling. Below there is a table where is shown the importance of cooling in Spain, since in the EU there are 91.60 cooling degree-days in 2018, while in Spain there are more than 2.5 times cooling degree-days, specifically 239.15, being among the highest in the EU.

	2009	2010	2011	2012	2013	2014	2015	2016	2017	2018
European Union - 28 countries	76.02	89.84	72.57	108.32	79.45	54.16	114.88	87.31	104.78	91.60
Belgium	7.69	18.81	8.62	13.34	16.03	8.91	29.87	23.26	16.86	33.12
Bulgaria	116.73	180.24	127.88	274.37	134.07	102.30	193.65	183.45	206.96	125.54
Czechia	4.51	26.91	13.26	24.02	45.01	9.67	96.77	10.40	22.27	45.81
Denmark	0.11	2.19	0.00	0.38	0.52	1.45	0.10	0.46	0.00	13.95
Germany (until 1990 former territories)	4.38	31.79	8.55	15.44	27.64	10.50	54.76	15.70	8.82	51.22
Estonia	0.00	42.12	13.94	6.33	3.46	9.12	0.00	1.62	0.00	25.57
Ireland	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00
Greece	278.64	350.57	313.85	443.64	319.21	270.20	331.13	349.51	349.63	306.20
Spain	243.23	238.45	220.94	268.36	204.99	171.39	286.79	278.25	306.91	239.15
France	42.48	36.58	31.53	44.44	41.25	17.03	75.94	47.98	66.40	64.86
Croatia	118.56	124.63	153.94	231.50	153.12	59.22	222.22	113.73	206.69	144.58
Italy	244.79	194.84	212.01	309.85	201.10	125.13	305.13	200.83	295.40	232.67
Cyprus	704.91	732.18	662.65	767.71	682.76	600.89	642.73	732.63	702.58	805.71
Latvia	0.23	47.32	7.99	9.36	5.04	14.79	4.19	4.75	0.63	23.48
Lithuania	2.25	56.87	5.16	18.91	9.07	24.73	15.41	7.48	4.63	24.68
Luxembourg	11.68	33.97	11.88	22.13	27.49	14.22	69.06	19.14	23.08	47.19
Hungary	72.98	97.49	91.78	179.09	115.46	50.11	195.84	63.23	142.91	124.49
Malta	575.74	499.27	534.71	781.42	629.81	648.51	685.57	614.23	673.29	625.71
Netherlands	6.24	15.73	5.44	9.01	11.96	8.38	16.03	13.29	5.79	31.38
Austria	9.87	25.16	18.25	31.15	46.37	9.75	67.31	12.28	34.91	32.60
Poland	5.55	44.64	6.73	29.41	28.47	22.09	63.38	16.84	19.64	29.66
Portugal	190.34	261.96	141.68	166.63	240.39	96.15	182.02	275.88	269.43	233.23
Romania	75.01	131.77	79.04	209.28	90.31	61.55	165.74	107.72	131.25	84.93
Slovenia	22.79	44.70	44.60	80.61	87.49	11.46	106.01	32.41	87.43	51.12
Slovakia	22.99	45.36	33.31	80.43	61.75	19.28	119.10	26.99	59.89	53.04
Finland	0.00	15.63	2.19	0.38	1.08	2.36	0.00	0.00	0.00	8.76
Sweden	0.01	1.33	0.02	0.01	0.02	1.27	0.00	0.00	0.00	4.51
United Kingdom	0.10	0.00	0.17	0.28	0.27	0.02	0.80	0.41	0.22	1.09

Table 3.7 Cooling Degree Days per EU Countries (2009-2018)

In spite of this, cooling has a low representation in Spain's demand because even with higher cooling demands and lower heating demands than in the rest of Europe, in 2018 there were 7,5 times more heating degree days than cooling degree days. Besides, there are more heating installations in buildings than cooling, but the situation is changing, and cooling installations are increasing. In fact, looking towards 2050, the current policy is ambitious regarding space cooling, but overall does not reduce the energy demand for heating and cooling. And considering that cooling is the fastest growing part of the heating and cooling sector, it is not expected to represent more than 40% of the heating and cooling sector in Spain in 2050. Space cooling is expected to double towards 2050 (from 59,3 to 125,4 TWh), the majority of which in the service sector. In terms of space cooling in the residential sector a six-fold increase is expected, but in absolute terms less than 55% of the 2050 demand is expected to be in the residential sector. This means that while the growth for demand is very high (especially

compared to space heating, where extremely substantial reductions in demand are considered for 2050), the heating and cooling sector overall is still dominated by space and process heating.

Figure 1.10 Delivered heating and cooling demands in 2015, and in two scenarios in 2050. Heating and cooling sector in Spain.

Gas and electricity prices

Currently the gas has a great representation for heating in Spain. According to the scenarios, there will be an increase of electricity demand for heat pumps, and therefore in the peak electricity load. The heating and cooling sector in forecast scenarios are deeply connected with the electricity sector through the use of combined heat and power and heat pumps.

However, the electricity that is used for heat pumps generally reflects the supply mix of the electricity sector, and includes a high level of variable renewables; shares of biomass combustion and an amount fossil fuels, and an evolution of this mix is foreseen to be oriented towards renewable energies.

Next, gas and electricity prices (without and with taxes) have been analysed. Currently, most of the heating is covered by gas boilers, although electricity demand is expected to increase, and gas demand is expected to decrease in the coming years.

in 2018 S2 (2nd Semester) gas price in Spain represented the second highest cost in Europe after Sweden. It was 43% more expensive than the European average. When taxes are taken into account, gas price in Spain in 2018 (S2) was the fourth most expensive, being 31% more expensive than the European average.

Electricity prices in Spain in 2018 (S2) without tax is the third highest cost in all of Europe after Ireland and Belgium. In this case the electricity cost is much higher than the average cost of the EU, a 47% more expensive. With taxes included in the analysis in 2018 (S2), electricity price in Spain is the fifth most expensive country, being 17% more expensive than the European average.

Although both gas and electricity prices are higher than the European average in a similar proportion, there is still a majority use of gas in Spain probably because is considerably cheaper than electricity. In 2018 (S2), in Spain electricity has been a 2.8 times more expensive than gas.

Importance of passive measures

After analysing the particularities of Spanish heating and cooling buildings, and especially after knowing the high percentage which represents heating and cooling in the final energy demand and the cooling importance in comparison with rest of Europe, it seems logical that energy efficiency in heating and cooling systems should be improved in Spain. Besides, energy efficiency and smart buildings are closely related. It would be interesting taking into account some architectural measures as correct shape and orientation of the building, correct windows location, solar protection, use of suitable materials and walls, building envelope thermal insulation, air renovation, roof gardens...With this type of measures buildings demands would decrease, which would lead to energy savings and consequently to a reduction of equipment needed to offer comfort in the buildings which also depends on gas or electricity, and which are more expensive in Spain than in European average.

Market in Spain

At the moment, there is only one GEOTABS project located in Spain. The project is situated in Tres Cantos (Madrid) and the owner is REE (Red Eléctrica de España), the Spanish National Electricity Grid Company.

The whole project consists of the integral refurbishment of two buildings located in the Tres Cantos Technology Park (Madrid). The project includes the integral rehabilitation of the buildings, adapting them to the new training and technological needs of the company, by modernizing the buildings using an envelope that meets the energy efficiency requirements. The two buildings have a total built area of 6,000 m2.

Regarding the active strategy applied to the building, the GEOTABS solution includes a thermal activation of the existing structure and an energy exchange system based on geothermal technology. The only production system consists on several heat pumps connected to a geothermal vertical borehole field, to provide 100% of heating and cooling demand to the buildings.

Very good comfort and energy efficiency results were achieved, and the environmental impact of the rehabilitation is minimal.

The main project agents are:

Project agents	
Developer	Red Eléctrica Corporación S.A.
Engineering	Idom Ingeniería and Consultoría S.A.U.
Project Management	Idom Ingeniería and Consultoría S.A.U.
Stakeholders	Grupo Avintia, Ferrovial, Strunor, Geotermia Vertical, Cortizo

Table 2.8 main GEOTABS agents in Spain.

About the future, in March 2020, GEOTER is aware of the existing (and trying to participate) of two more buildings, located in Spain, designed following GEOTABS guidelines. The construction of them is planned by the end of the year.

Expectations about the future of GEOTABS systems in Spain is high. Spanish market in building sector uses to integrate Central and North European tendencies but at a slow pace. because of the Spanish particularities. Cooling control and optimization of TABS will be decisive for the faster development of the GEOTABS solutions in Spain.

Conclusion

Heating and cooling demand in Spain represents about 40% of final energy demand. Inside heating and cooling, Spain is characterized by having more than double of cooling degree days compared to Europe and about 60% less of heating degree days compared to Europe. However, cooling demands are less significant compared to heating demand; even in Spain in 2018, heating degree days were 7,5 times higher than cooling degree days. Anyway, it is expected a cooling demand increase in the future.

Regarding current heating systems, boilers are predominant, and electric heating has a great presence. It is expected a decrease of gas and an increase of electric heating, but especially an increase of heat pumps is expected. Regarding current cooling systems, split units, large split units, and chillers of varying sizes are predominant. The main advantage of the heat pumps is that it can provide heating and cooling, so are the most interesting option for the future.

In this possible evolution the price of gas and electricity will affect, being currently electricity almost three times more expensive than gas in Spain. In addition, if Spain data are compared with average European data, Spain is more expensive both in terms of gas and electricity (in higher proportions in gas than in electricity).

Given these characteristics, it seems interesting that in Spain passive measures and heat pumps must be taken into account for the optimization of buildings considering the country conditions.

3.5.3. Scandinavia

The development and installations of TABS in Scandinavian countries are mostly in Norway, see figure 3.11.

Figure 3.11: Top 5 TABS countries in Europe (Source: adapted from Euroconstruct & International Energy Agency)

Acceptance and awareness are mostly well established in German-speaking countries, or climates with mild heating and cooling. In principle, TABS are primary used as a cooling system, as a result, regions with high heating demand, or long heating season more than 3 months commonly use TABS as a basic option, or other competitive solutions.

Figure 3.12: TABS in Total Surface Heating & Cooling in Europe (Source: adapted from Euroconstruct & International Energy Agency)

3.5.4. Belgium

In Belgium one of the first GEOTABS concepts was introduced in a residential project end of the 20th century (Haus DF in Kortrijk, arch. Beel, Boydens engineering). Already VITO was elaborating GEOTABS within their R&D on larger scale, looking at office and elderly home applications, mainly in a strategy for making a spin off for shallow geothermal installations, Terra Energy (ir. Hans Hoes), that is one of the current market players. However the GEOTABS combination was not put in to practice at that time. Boydens engineering has introduced the concept after attending two Velta (now Uponor) conferences in Austria, and the Anwenderforum Oberflächennähe Geothermie organized by OTTI in Freising, Bavaria. Inspired by prof Bjarne Olesen, R&D of Velta at that time, they have searched for implementations in offices, the first being new offices for the company Oiltanking in Antwerp, in 2003.

Although VITO had performed feasibility studies on elderly homes for GEOTABS, the first real GEOTABS elderly home designed by Boydens engineering was opened in Belgium, Moorsele in 2009, and several other elderly homes followed quickly (Turnhout, Belsele, ...). Several engineering offices started to discover the concept and tried out first designs. The main bigger implementations were offices for Infrac (now Fluvius) in Torhout (design VK engineering) and Dilbeek, Brussels (design Boydens engineering), both opened 2011-2012.

In the same period prof Lieve Helsen (KU Leuven) launched the EU-FP7-EraSME project GEOTABS, where Boydens engineering joined as a partner as well as several other Belgian engineering offices (Heedfeld, VK engineering, ...) in the user committee. The aim was to bring design and control to a higher level.

The project was immediately followed by SmartGeotherm (a IWT funded deployment project, 2011-2017, with the research group of prof. Helsen as main research partner, together with BBRI and VITO), where further steps were incentivised, be it on shallow geothermal projects in general, but with special attention on GEOTABS projects.

Results of this trajectory was an increase of geothermal driller companies from 23 to 38, HVAC installers counted a significant increase to geothermal applications (300 companies) and a wide adoption of the concept by architects and engineering offices was noticed, leading to about 1.200 larger projects in that timeframe.

The governmental EPBD compliance scheme initialized an adoption of assessment of geothermal cooling in their approach.

The increase of implementation of GEOTABS did however not follow an exponential path, mainly due to investment costs, required engineering and simulation skills and upfront investment, and the hesitance to invest time in finetuning of the control after the inhousing of the building. These barriers are exactly the main drivers for Boydens engineering, KU Leuven and Ghent university to set up the hybridGEOTABS proposal, together with DTU and Energoklastr, that were involved in the first GEOTABS project as well.

During the project hybridGEOTABS period some flagship governmental hybridGEOTABS buildings were constructed, with high architectural appearance, demonstrating the multiple advantages of the concept: the Herman Teirlinck building in Brussels (Flemish government), BIM building in Brussels (Brussels government) and the house of Province in Antwerp (Antwerp Province administration building).

Due to the further MPC developments in the rather late stage of the project the control in these buildings still is an RBC control, but the buildings are targets to be control-retrofitted and to be demonstrators of the results in the further focus of enerCORE deployment.

4. Control Practice

In this chapter, control technologies currently used in hybridGEOTABS buildings as well as their limits are discussed. For such buildings with many energy sources and sinks, displaying nonlinear dynamic thermal behaviour, rule based controllers are standard practise. This can lead to a wide range of energy performance, depending on the expertise of the control engineering team and the time available to monitor the building, re-adjust the controls to reach best performance over time. Recent developments in Model Predictive Control (MPC) are also mentioned in the last part of this chapter, which present a very promising alternative solution for hybrid building solutions.

4.1. Heat pump control

4.1.1. Rule Based Control (RBC)

The heat pump with a Rule Based Controller (RBC) controls its compressor status based on the buffer tank sensor set point. This set point can be defined based on an external 0-10V signal, a heating curve per secondary system (the maximum supply temperature of all curves will be the set point of applied to the buffer tank sensor) or a fixed value. The following graph shows the working principle of an on-off heat pump in combination with a buffer tank.

Figure 4.1 Control of an on/off heat pump with a buffer tank

- A. Temperature set point buffer tank
- B. Hysteresis temperature heating buffer tank
- C. Set point compressor: 100% for on-off compressors
- D. Running time switching-off based on upper buffer temperature sensor
- E. Running time switching-off based on lower buffer temperature sensor

If a multi stage heat pump is applied the following rules are taken into account before start-up of a compressor

- First of all, a heat demand should be present. The set temperature of the relevant consumer is undershot by the corresponding start hysteresis
- Then the controller checks if the blocking time of 20 min since the last compressor was started has expired.
 - If not, the compressor(s) will not start (This indicates a wrong sizing of the HP or water content of the buffer tank).
 - If the blocking time is passed, the multistage heat pump will allow the first compressor to work.
- The order of starting up a compressor takes into account which compressor worked last. This algorithm is needed to reach the same amount of working hours at the end of the life cycle of the heat pump.
- The final start-up of the compressor is defined by a parameter (730E). The Kmin-integral I_L will be compared to this parameter.
 - When $I_L > 0,5$ times the integral (Kmin undershooting of the buffer tank set point) the first compressor will start.
 - If the power of this first stage is not sufficient and the set point not reached, the integral keeps growing and after 1 time the integra the second stages will work.
- To avoid a nervous start-stop behaviour, a second blocking time of 5 min since stopping the most recently started compressor is added in the controller. This value avoids the second stage to start up to soon.

The compressors start according to the following system, depending on the output integral I_L :

System for compressor demand

Output integral I_L	Compressor	
	①	②
$I_L > 0.5$ times the "Start threshold 730E"	ON	OFF
$I_L > \text{"Start threshold 730E"}$	ON	ON

- ① Compressor 1: The compressor started first
- ② Compressor 2: The compressor started last
- I_L Output integral: The integral of the duration and extent of the deviation between the set and actual return temperature in the secondary circuit

Figure 4.2 Compressor start logic

If the stop conditions for the relevant consumer have been reached, the compressors switch off, depending on the output integral I_L :

System for switching off the compressors

Output integral I_L	Compressor	
	①	②
$I_L < \text{"Start threshold 730E"}$	ON	ON
$I_L < 0.5$ times the "Start threshold 730E"	OFF	ON
$I_L = 0$	OFF	OFF

- ① Compressor 1: The compressor started first
- ② Compressor 2: The compressor started last
- I_L Output integral: The integral of the duration and extent of the deviation between the set and actual return temperature in the secondary circuit

Figure 4.3 Compressor stop logic

4.1.2. Bivalent mode operation

The heat pump control unit enables the bivalent mode operation of the heat pump with an external heat source, e.g. external boiler. The external heat generator is ideally hydraulically connected in such a way that the heat pump can also be used as a return temperature raising facility for the boiler. System separation is provided with a buffer cylinder. For optimum heat pump operation, the external heat generator must be integrated into the system flow downstream from the buffer cylinder via a mixer. The heat pump control unit controls this mixer directly.

Different ways to control the external heat demand exists. One of them uses the following logic: The heat pump control unit enables operation of the external heat generator for central heating if the adjusted outside temperature is below the "Dual mode temperature external heat source".

Above the dual mode temperature, the external heat generator only starts under the following conditions:

- The heat pump fails to start due to a fault
- There is a special heat demand, e.g. frost protection

Start criteria:

The system flow temperature is crucial for the starting of the external heat generator. In order to prevent brief undershooting of the set value resulting in the immediate start of the external heat generator, the output integral is used as start criterion (integral resulting from the duration and amount of the deviation between the set and actual flow temperature). In the following cases, the start of the external heat generator will be prevented for the duration of a fixed programmed time:

- After a change in the "Time program heating" from one operating state with low set temperature to a higher set temperature, e.g. from "Reduced" to "Standard"
- After changeover between central heating and DHW heating

Regulating the system flow temperature:

The mixer for linking in the external heat generator remains closed until the boiler water temperature of the external heat generator has reached a programmed minimum flow temperature. This prevents cold heating water from the external heat generator reaching the heating circuits. After opening, the mixer regulates towards the set flow temperature of the system.

Stop criteria:

The heat pump control unit switches the external heat generator off if both of the following conditions are met:

- Min. runtime external heat source has expired
- The system flow temperature is above the set value for a programmed duration

4.2. hybridGEOTABS building controls – current and best practice

Current and best practice features of RBC in hybridGEOTABS buildings are listed, based on current strategies observed in multiple hybridGEOTABS buildings.

- Climate modes: TABS are massive structures which have high inertia. Hence, it is not desirable to freely change the supply temperature set-point towards the pipes embedded in the concrete, since noticing the

effects of such an action can take from several hours to more than a day. To cope with this feature using traditional rules, TABS are usually operated based on a climate mode: either heating, cooling or neutral mode. The transition between modes occurs once per day based on the running mean outdoor temperature of the previous days, although it is always possible to switch manually between the different modes. These temperatures where the transition happens can vary in function of the building use. For instance, elderly care homes usually have higher temperature set points, so their transition temperature towards cooling will be higher. A common feature is that directly changing from heating to cooling mode, or vice-versa, is not possible: a step day through the neutral mode is needed.

- **TABS:** TABS operate based on the selected climate mode. TABS control has two degrees of freedom: the supply water temperature, typically achieved by a mixing 3-way valve, and the water mass flow rate through the embedded pipes, controlled either by a 2-way valve or a modulating hydraulic pump. The total number of degrees of freedom, and consequently their control, is dependent on the distribution system installed. Common distribution configurations include: building level control (two degrees of freedom for the whole building), (ii) floor level control (at least one of the degrees of freedom is controlled per floor) and (iii) zone level control (at least one of the degrees of freedom is controlled per zone), typically distinguishing between the north and south zones of the same floor to cope with the different heat gains due to solar radiation. Besides, not only 2-pipe but also 4-pipe configurations exist to prevent simultaneous heating and cooling, thereby increasing the number of degrees of freedom in the system. Nevertheless, on the higher level, TABS control has common features. The supply water temperature is calculated by a heating curve as a function of the running mean outdoor temperature, i.e. the same that determines the climate mode. Compensation factors can be included to take the current building zone temperatures into account. Condensation should be avoided in cooling mode (when TABS are used in humid climates). The water mass flow rate through the embedded pipes is controlled based on the temperature difference between the supply and return temperature. If this difference is small, the heat exchange between TABS and building zones is very small, leading to a re-adjustment of the mass flow rate. In neutral mode, hydraulic pumps still work for equalization purposes.
- **Ground source heat pump (GSHP):** Due to the size and heating/cooling requirements of hybridGEOTABS buildings, they can have multiple GSHPs with two or more stages. In a hybridGEOTABS building, they can be connected not only to TABS but also to the secondary system and/or air based system of the building. Therefore, they have to provide at least the highest of the set-points that these systems request to the buffer tank. If the set-point is not achieved after a specific period of time, the next GSHP/stage will be turned on. The condenser-side hydraulic pump works at nominal conditions whenever the GSHP is on. The evaporator-side hydraulic pump modulates the mass flow rate depending on the stage level of the GSHP. If the GSHP is off (passive cooling), the evaporator-side hydraulic pump modulates depending on the temperature difference between the inlet and the outlet of the geothermal borefield. When the outlet temperature of the borefield is above a set value, seasonal energy storage of the borefield has been depleted and as a consequence the GSHP is turned on in reverse mode to provide active cooling.
- **Secondary system:** Since a large variety of secondary systems exists from both the supply and emission point of view, it is more difficult to define common features. However, it is clear that the secondary system is independent of the climate mode of the building, since it needs to be fast-reacting under sudden changes of the building load. The control of the secondary system is a function of the zone-level temperature or instant ambient temperature.

- **Ventilation:** Ventilation, which can also be used as the secondary system, is also independent of the climate mode of the building. The air mass flow rates of the ventilation system are calculated to cover at least the hygienic standards established by each country. Its heating and cooling curves depend on the instant ambient temperature. Being air-based, these curves have the feature that their slope is very small, i.e. they provide a narrow range of supply temperatures. The combination of a PI control, a thermal recovery system and the heating/cooling coils of the ventilation unit provide these desired air supply temperatures. Night ventilation is usually programmed to almost freely cool down the building during summer season.

Energy-efficient heat production technologies such as heat pumps, combined with low-temperature heat emission systems, allow the heat conversion efficiency to increase, which further reduces the primary energy demand. Low-temperature emission systems such as floor heating or thermally activated building systems (TABS) increase the thermal mass of buildings. The increased thermal mass and insulation levels increase the thermal time constants of buildings. This includes the time constants of the emission system when using TABS. New buildings are therefore harder to control using rule-based control (RBC) systems that use control logic such as hysteresis controllers, PI(D)s and heating curves, which do not inherently integrate system delays and forecasts. Moreover, RBC strategies typically do not anticipate the impact of future disturbances on the current control action, or the impact of the current control action on future system states and therefore on the future system control action. This incurs an efficiency loss since thermal loads can be shifted in time when production is either more efficient or when a different heat source can be used. New buildings typically have more complex thermal systems, which have many degrees of freedom such as valve openings, pump speeds and supply temperature set points (Jorissen et al. 2019). A single degree of freedom often affects many zones of such buildings and coordinating between these different interests is hard for an RBC. This may cause conservative set points to be used in order to satisfy the zone that needs the largest control action, which can lead to an excessive control action for other zones, e.g. when using return water temperature controlled two-way valves for a set of parallel TABS circuits, an increase in the supply water temperature demand for one TABS slab, will increase the heat delivered to all TABS slabs. Secondary systems may automatically compensate for this, which can, e.g. lead to simultaneous heating and cooling of the same zone. In addition to an increase in the primary energy use of such buildings, thermal comfort may not be provided, e.g. due to overheating caused by solar gains or by insufficient secondary capacity to compensate an excessive control action of the primary system. Such problems can cause an uncomfortable environment in buildings in general, and a loss of productivity in office buildings, which has indirect financial implications (Verhelst 2017; Wargorcki et al. 2006). Badly performing RBCs can lead to long commissioning periods and possibly even to the installation of extra secondary systems. This further increases the total cost of ownership of a building, and can even lead to energy efficient devices being switched off in favour of secondary systems, or a malfunction of the energy-efficient device or the controller may go unnoticed if the secondary device takes over. Moreover, the underground thermal balance in the borefield should be guaranteed to ensure long-term sustainable operation of the hybridGEOTABS systems. Up to now this is covered by sizing the borefield large enough. However, in hybrid systems that are controlled by predictive controllers that take both short and long term objectives into account, these control strategies may facilitate smaller borefield sizes without harming the long-term sustainable operation. This illustrates that state-of-the-art RBCs are not always capable to cope with the complexity of contemporary thermal systems in buildings, such as hybridGEOTABS (Jorissen et al. 2019).

4.3. Model Predictive Control (MPC) recent developments

Model predictive control (MPC) is fundamentally a different type of controller, that has the potential to solve many, if not all, of the aforementioned problems. MPC is a control strategy that optimizes a system's control

inputs using a computer mathematical model of the system such that a cost function is minimized. Constraints can be enforced to bound the allowed solution space of the optimization problem. MPC can be applied to building control problems (Jorissen et al. 2019). It then typically minimizes the energy use or energy cost of the building, while enforcing constraints such as technical constraints and comfort constraints, but other cost functions are possible too. Figure 4.4 gives a schematic presentation of MPC applied to a hybridGEOTABS building.

Figure 4.4: Schematic presentation of MPC (Source: Damien Picard, KU Leuven)

MPC has already been realized for building applications. Real implementations of MPC have demonstrated energy savings of 17% in a Swiss office building (Sturzenegger et al. 2013, 2016), 17% in a Belgian office building in Hasselt (Váňa et al. 2014), more than 30% in a Belgian office building in Brussels (De Coninck and Helsen 2016), 19% and 27% in two Australian office buildings (West, Ward, and Wall 2014), and 15–28% in a Czech building (Cigler et al. 2013; Prívvara et al. 2011; Široký et al. 2011), all with a similar or improved thermal comfort. Hilliard, Kavgic, and Swan (2016) present a review of recent MPC strategies. Clearly, there is a **large potential for energy savings using MPC while at the same time improving thermal comfort**, although the potential depends on the building type and the reference compared with (Cigler et al. 2013). Despite numerous demonstrations of MPC in buildings, commercially exploiting this potential is difficult due to the large amount of work incurred by setting up the MPC controller model (Cigler et al. 2013; Sturzenegger et al. 2014). An MPC development strategy that is both practical and scalable to large problem sizes has not been demonstrated to date. Further research is therefore required to **simplify MPC controller model development**, for instance, through the development of a convenient framework for setting up MPC controller models, as was also mentioned by the editorial of Henze

(2013): "the question begs whether the time has come for a **unified and open-source software environment for building MPC**". We impose the following requirements for such a framework.

- 1) Controller model development should be fast.
- 2) Expert knowledge can be required for component model development, but no expert knowledge should be required for developing MPC models using combinations of these component models. That is, models should be object-oriented, such that they are generic and easy to combine by users, and easy to maintain by developers.
- 3) The framework should be scalable to large problems, with reasonable computation times.
- 4) The resulting MPC should be exportable and robust.
- 5) The framework preferably leverages existing standards and tools such that it is future-proof.

Sturzenegger et al. (2012, 2014) presented **Building Resistance-Capacitance Modelling (BRM)**, a Matlab toolbox for setting up bilinear building envelope MPC models and input data using basic building construction data contained in an EnergyPlus input file. The toolbox however does not provide a generic way for modelling building HVAC equipment. De Coninck et al. (2016) presented a toolbox for identifying the parameters of low-order '**grey-box**' **RC building models** using building measurement data. This approach however requires measurement data of high quality with few unmodelled disturbances and large excitations and has not yet been demonstrated for multi-zone problems. The grey-box toolbox uses Modelica (Elmqvist and Mattsson 1997), an object-oriented equation-based modelling language. Although the initial scope of Modelica is to perform dynamic simulations, tools such as JModelica (Åkesson et al. 2010) and OpenModelica (Fritzsion et al. 2005) also allow derivative-based optimization of such models, which can be used to implement an optimal control problem (OCP) (Bonvini and Wetter 2015) or MPC (De Coninck and Helsen 2016). These tools however use general-purpose solvers and algorithms, which do not exploit the linear nature and structure of our MPC optimization problems. This reduces computation speed and therefore scalability. Jorissen and Helsen (2016) developed a **linear automated toolchain for MPC (LAT-MPC)**, which uses a linear (Picard, Jorissen, and Helsen 2015) building model that is implemented using the Modelica library IDEAS (Jorissen et al. 2018). LAT-MPC only supports linear models since the model is extracted by computing the system's state space model using finite differences of the state variables and outputs with respect to the model inputs (Picard, Jorissen, and Helsen 2015). LAT-MPC was applied to an office building model that consists of 24 zones and 1330 states. The HVAC models were also linearized. Post-processing is required to map the linear HVAC model degrees of freedom (e.g. flow rates) into the system degrees of freedom (e.g. valve positions). Developing a LAT-MPC therefore still requires more optimal control and modelling expertise than what can be expected from the intended users. Moreover, the solution for the case study is suboptimal due to the conservative model approximations that were used.

These issues can be avoided by using **non-linear MPC problems**. JModelica implements a full Modelica parser and can thus be used to develop non-linear MPC problems. The JModelica optimization parser however does not support discrete decision variables or the Modelica Standard Library data reader (CombiTimeTable), which is used in the IDEAS weather data reader. Moreover, JModelica implements collocation by default, which approximates state and algebraic variables using piecewise polynomials and a fine-grained temporal discretization (Åkesson et al. 2010). Such a fine discretization is expected to result in larger computation times for multi-zone building models, which have in the order of a thousand state variables and thousands of algebraic variables. Due to the reasons outlined above, **TACO**, a toolchain that generates optimization code from a Modelica model implemented using libraries such as the IDEAS and the IBPSA (Annex 6a) library (Wetter and van Treeck 2017) has been developed. TACO is a modified version of JModelica that includes modifications that allow the use of data readers. TACO further implements a new and efficient problem formulation that exploits the near-linear nature of building dynamics, but also allows the use of steady-state non-linear HVAC models. For a discussion of numerical optimization algorithms and principles we refer the reader to Nocedal and Wright (1999) and Diehl (2014). With TACO a methodology that greatly facilitates the development of MPCs in practice

is being developed. The implementation of TACO (white-box MPC) is demonstrated in 2 buildings (office and elderly care home) and the implementation of a grey-box approach is demonstrated in 1 building (school) within the hybridGEOTABS project.

Going beyond today's best practice, the latest development in the field of white-box MPC applied to buildings is discussed in the next section with some preliminary results of the white-box MPC running in an office building near Brussels (Belgium) shown in Figure 4.6 and Figure 4.7.

4.3.1. MPC - White Box Approach (Infracx office)

The Infracx building has 2232 m² of floor space spread over 4 floors.

This office building contains open-plan offices, cellular offices and meeting rooms. The building envelope has high level of insulation with double-glazed windows, reducing passively the building heating and cooling requirements.

Figure 4.5 below shows the hydraulic scheme of the building. Thermal energy is produced by means of 2 geothermal heat pumps of 70 kW_{th} each. The source-side of the heat pumps is connected to a geothermal borefield that is composed of 38 vertical double-U boreholes of 94 m each. The sink-side of the heat pumps is connected to a 2500 l water storage tank and to a main collector, where heat is distributed to multiple distribution loops. In an initial stage, the building was designed to store and cool several server units. Consequently, a 150 kW cooling tower is installed on the source-side to relieve the cooling load of the borefield when needed. Due to the low demand of domestic hot water, a small electrical boiler is installed. The building has a hybrid emission system that is composed of TABS as a hydronic slow-reacting base load system and of an air handling unit (AHU) that can heat or cool as an air-based, fast-reacting secondary system.

The AHU has a nominal supply volumetric flow rate of 10 000 m³/h and a nominal extraction volumetric flow rate of 8850 m³/h. The AHU is equipped with heating and cooling coils of 34 kW and 59 kW respectively, and a heat recovery wheel placed between these coils. The air is distributed over the zones of the building; of which some are equipped with Variable Air Volume (VAV) boxes. Air can be re-heated if needed by using heating coils inside the ducts. For heating, the aforementioned collector distributes the thermal energy to 4 different heating loops: to the VAV heating coils in the air distribution system (45 kW), to the heating coil of the AHU (34 kW), to the TABS system (60 kW) and to the cooling tower (150 kW) in case of dissipation. For cooling, the source side is connected through counter flow plate heat exchangers to the TABS system (90 kW), and to the cooling coil of the AHU and to the server units (106 kW).

Figure 4.5: Simplified hydronic schematic of the Infrac office building.

Since May 24, 2019, the aforementioned office building is controlled by the MPC developed with TACO. While the energy savings still have to be quantified, preliminary results shows that temperatures of all the zones of the building are successfully maintained between the comfort bounds (see Figure 4.3.2). Beside good comfort, Figure 4.3.3 illustrates that MPC reduces the fan power of the air handling unit by a factor 2 in the considered period.

Figure 4.6: Measured temperature of the different zones and their comfort bounds for the office building controlled by MPC.

Figure 4.7: Fan power of the air handling unit of the office building while controlled by RBC and by MPC.

White-box MPC has a lot of strengths, among them: operation at optimal system efficiency and/or low electricity tariff, different and multiple objectives possible - among them sustainability and cost, control of the system as a whole instead of device by device, more energy savings thanks to the use of detailed models, avoid 'destruction of energy' thanks to anticipation, avoid overheating and undercooling, as well as bad indoor air quality, RBC becomes obsolete so no BMS tuning is needed, potential for automated commissioning and fault detection. Most of these strengths can also be observed in the grey-box MPC approach, though the controller model is less detailed which may lead to smaller energy savings and more difficult fault detection. The detailed models of the white-box approach, however, need to be developed. For this step a semi-automated approach needs to be set up. The long-term sustainable operation of the underground is now being added to the concept.

4.3.2. MPC – Grey Box Approach (Libeznice School)

The Libeznice school is recently built in 2015 building and is composed of 8 classrooms for 240 pupils in total (each classroom is for 30 pupils) as well as of multi-functional hall used as a canteen or for cultural events. The building itself is called "Rondel" due to it represents the Solar System and forms "Sun" in the centre and 8 planets" around 8 classrooms. The GEOTABS system is controlled by a model predictive controller (MPC) that considers weather forecast, model of thermodynamics of the heat pump and TABS.

Heating system is composed of ground source heat pump (GSHP) of 57.9 kW (Bo/W35). Heat pump has on/off controller. The primary side is connected to 6 U-tube boreholes each of 130 m depth, however the secondary side is connected to domestic hot water (DHW) and space heating (SH) storage tanks of 500 l each. The above-mentioned storage tanks serve as buffers between the heat and cold sources and the customer. The heat pump is controlled by signals from the temperature sensors installed at the storage tanks at relative height of 0.7 and 0.3, respectively, for SH and space cooling (SC) storage tanks with the dead band of 4 K. The GSHP primary side is additionally equipped with electric boiler of 24 kW as a bivalent heat source, which is however not used in practice. Further, the hot water is distributed to the TABS and AHU. Moreover, heat can be released from SH storage tank to the borefield via brazed plate heat exchanger (BPHX) (see Fig. 4.8). The primary side of GSHP is also connected to the cold storage tank used when cooling load takes place. The cool from SC storage tank is distributed to the TABS and AHU and used when there is SC load. The ventilation system is composed of 8 identical AHU for each classroom, every AHU has heating coil of 3.69 kW and cooling coil of 1.72 kW and volumetric ow rate of 780 m³/h. Additionally one more AHU is installed to supply the corridor, canteen and

common areas with fresh air of volumetric flow rate of 2380 m³/h (heating coil of 17.1 kW and cooling coil of 7.2 kW). Thus, heat and cool is distributed via TABS and AHU system loops and DHW preparation system. The designed power of systems above indicated are as follows:

TABS Power:

- o Heating 17.4 kW
- o Cooling 23.5 kW

AHU Power:

- o Heating 46.6 kW
- o Cooling 21 Kw

The HVAC systems are schematically presented in Figure 4.8.

Figure 4.8: Libeznice hydraulic scheme

The new MPC implementation in a school Libeznice (Czech Republic) was put into operation on 15th October 2018. The main changes compared to the previous MPC implementation are:

- MPC controls both TABS and ventilation system
- Grey-box temperature and CO₂ model for each class

Some preliminary results of the grey-box MPC running in Libeznice school are presented here. As seen on Figure 4.9, the first results show that the classroom temperatures are maintained within the bounds 21°C – 24°C in winter season. The MPC setpoint in winter season is 22°C with the night and weekend setback 21°C.

Figure 4.9: Measured temperatures in each classroom and their comfort bounds in Libeznice school during the heating season controlled by MPC.

As the school is also open during the summer holidays as a centre for summer camps, it makes sense to evaluate the thermal comfort in summer season too. As seen on Fig. 4.10 the temperatures in classrooms are maintained in the bounds 22-24°C, however they exceed 24°C in June where there are high solar and occupancy gains. Moreover, the ambient temperature exceeds 30°C and MPC operates TABS on maximum power. During summer camps in July and August the classroom temperatures are maintained more often in the comfort bounds (excluding periods with heat pump problems) as there are less children (lower occupancy gains) compared to the normal school year.

Figure 4.10: Measured temperatures in each classroom in Libeznice school during summer controlled by MPC.

Since the power of AHUs is not directly measured in Libeznice school, the first comparison of new and old MPC implementation was performed for TABS operation only. The evaluation was performed separately for heating and cooling season.

The evaluation for heating season is shown in first table below. The power of MPC was normalized to the same ambient temperature as in the season with old MPC implementation. It can be seen that the average TABS power is slightly higher for new MPC, however the average class temperature is much closer to setpoint 22°C, meaning that the thermal comfort was significantly improved during the heating season.

The second table shows the evaluation for summer (cooling) season. As can be shown, the average ambient temperature for old and new MPC is comparable (23.78 °C), therefore no normalization is needed in this case. The table shows that the building is operated with lower TABS power when using new MPC (approx. 4% savings of TABS energy) while keeping the same thermal comfort (average classroom temperatures is 23.45 °C).

	Average TABS power (kW)		Ambient temperature (°C)		Average class temperature (°C)	
	old MPC	new MPC	new MPC		old MPC	new MPC
November	6.99	5.99	6.32		23.15	22.88
December	7.09	8.06	4.6		22.99	22.47
January	8.58	9.36	1.82		23.05	22.4
February	6.78	7.25	4.24		22.81	22.64
Average	7.36	7.67	4.25		23	22.6

Table 4.1: Preliminary results of new MPC implementation in Libeznice school for heating season.

	Average TABS power (kW)		Ambient temperature (°C)		Average class temperature (°C)	
	old MPC	new MPC	old MPC	new MPC	old MPC	new MPC
June	9.01	11.18	22	25.19	24.12	23.8
July	9.88	7.88	24.61	23.49	23.22	23.64
August	8.12	6.77	24.71	22.65	23.14	22.92
Average	9	8.61	23.77	23.78	23.49	23.45

Table 4.2: Preliminary results of new MPC implementation in Libeznice school for cooling season.

5. Future Outlook

5.1. Towards a clean energy transition and grid flexibility

The hybridGEOTABS concept contributes to the three European goals regarding increasing energy efficiency (low exergy systems, optimally controlled, exchange of thermal flows), increasing share of renewable and residual energy sources (R²ES) (geothermal, potentially combined with solar and residual thermal flows) and decreasing greenhouse gas (GHG) emissions (thanks to the high energy efficiency and use of R²ES), and at the same time creating a comfortable environment in the building. As such the hybridGEOTABS concept plays a **crucial role in the path towards clean energy and even beyond.**

The intrinsic storage capacity, available in the building, TABS and underground, combined with the predictive control, offered by MPC, renders the hybridGEOTABS concept a **perfect candidate to offer flexibility** to the broader energy system. This allows to increase the R²ES share even further by using demand side flexibility. Two possibilities for demand side flexibility are illustrated in Figure 5.1 MPC has all features to unlock flexibility by **demand response** (shifting loads in time or changing loads in size to better match the available supply without jeopardizing thermal comfort), which may create substantial cost reductions by using electricity when it is cheap (operating cost), by flattening peaks (investment cost), by avoiding grid problems (grid stability and reliability) and high investments in the reinforcement and extension of electricity grid infrastructure (investment cost). Synergies can thus be exploited in multi-energy carrier systems thanks to the presence of thermal loads fed by electricity (such as heat pumps). Future scenarios extend this with electric vehicles (EV) providing in addition direct electricity storage. This leads us to the second option which uses the **energy storage** (thermal and/or electrical) available, resulting in a decoupling of demand and supply. The energy from R²ES is then stored when it is available, and used when it is needed, without changing the demand profile.

Figure 5.1: Illustration of the problem of mismatch in time between supply and demand, and two potential solutions: (middle) demand response, (right) energy storage. (Source: Anke Uytterhoeven, KU Leuven)

Figure 5.2 shows how the problem of peaking demand and supply can be tackled by relying upon demand side flexibility, in this case a combination of demand response and storage.

Figure 5.2: Solving the problem of peaking demand and supply by combining demand response and energy storage. (Source: Anke Uytterhoeven, KU Leuven)

By tackling the two aforementioned challenges via demand response, some important advantages are obtained. Firstly, the system's adequacy increases, as well as its stability. Since demand response is an attractive, cost effective balancing resource, some considerable investments can be reduced/avoided, being investments in i) expensive (and not so efficient) peak generation, in ii) local grid reinforcement and extension, and in iii) coal and gas fired spinning reserves. Consequently, the electricity systems and markets obtain a higher efficiency and are characterized by lower investment and operation costs. Secondly, because of the higher efficiency, and since available renewable energy sources are used more effectively, CO₂ (and other air pollutants) emissions are lowered. Finally, there is also something to gain for the end consumer. Since flexible demand can offer many advantages to the system and the market, it has a monetary value, leading to an additional income (Uytterhoeven et al. 2019).

The hybridGEOTABS concept involves multiple energy vectors: heat/cold, electricity and potentially also (green) gas or hydrogen in the hybrid part. This allows to extend the storage options even further by implementing power-to-X (where X can be heat, cold, methane, hydrogen ...) technologies that store electricity by conversion to another vector whenever it is cheaply available and use the energy vector (with or without further conversion) when demand is high. Furthermore, interactions between multiple grids (electricity, thermal, natural gas, hydrogen) need to be considered. All these options will contribute to the decarbonisation of heating, cooling and ventilation in buildings.

5.2. Outstanding practice

The innovation level of the **hybridGEOTABS** concept reaches its full potential when the following conditions are met:

- The share of geothermal resources is optimally sized to cover the heating and cooling baseloads.
- The geothermal resource is supplemented solely by the use of other, locally produced, renewable or residual energy sources, together covering 100% of the building energy requirements.
- The secondary emission system does not enter in conflict with the TABS as primary system (no simultaneous heating and cooling)
- When comfort and indoor environmental quality is guaranteed for the occupants all year round.
- When the balance in the ground is safeguarded.
- The design and control are not a barrier to the implementation of the project and life cycle costs are competitive.
- The theoretical energy performance and full potential is also achieved in operational practice, thanks to a good integration, operation and execution of all system components and controllers, a good communication and interaction with the user and user needs, throughout the life cycle of the building.
- The life cycle environmental performance of the building is optimised.
- Thermal storage (in the TABS, underground...) are optimally used to balance thermal loads on daily, weekly and yearly timeframe
- The hybridGEOTABS building interacts with the energy grids so that at building scale and larger scale, efficiencies, costs, energy availability are optimised (grid flexibility, peak shaving etc.). The MPC is directly used for this objective.

Conclusion

The strong political market drive towards energy savings in the building sector calls for truly efficient and innovative solutions. Due to the challenges faced by designers and investors as mentioned in chapter 2. and 3 of this report, the potential of hybridGEOTABS is often insufficiently exploited in current practice. In the recent years however, some new commercial building projects mainly in Germany, Switzerland and Sweden are setting examples, showing the potential of this concept and demonstrating how thermally activated structure coupled with the ground and other RES can reduce significantly the environmental impacts of buildings and create healthy, comfortable indoor environments. Recent developments in the field of model predictive control applied to buildings is also bringing an interesting solution to reduce commissioning cost and operate the systems to their full potential, harvesting even further savings.

In the hybridGEOTABS H2020 project, three ground-breaking solutions have been proposed and developed to tackle these challenges. First, the Consortium proposed the integration of GEOTABS with secondary emission and heating/cooling generation systems (hybrid concept) to remove identified barriers. Secondly, the a robust and adaptive model predictive control is implemented and a toolchain that allows to derive the model architecture and parameters semi-automatically is also being developed. Finally, the development of a holistic and easy-to-use procedure for feasibility and pre-design allowing optimal integration and sizing of hybridGEOTABS core components and secondary systems will be provided at the end of the project, therefore avoiding case-by-case simulation work and ensuring a better market uptake of the technology.

The hybridGEOTABS concept is an innovative concept and a new solution for decarbonising heating and cooling that demonstrate a significant improvement of the (hybrid)GEOTABS-RBC as seen across Europe (mainly in Austria, France, Germany, Sweden, Switzerland). It is controlled by MPC, uses clean energy sources and is supported by a new holistic design procedure with integrated design of required components, depending on building use and climate.

Pre-engineered design solutions enable quick sizing and selection of HVAC components based on a few specific building parameters. This is key to helping designer spend less time in the early design stages to demonstrate and quantify the advantages of such systems when compare to conventional (fossil fuel based) technologies.

A set of documents, such as various examples of hydraulic schemes and package information will also speed up the process of producing offers during Technical Design (RIBA stage 4) enabling a shorter tendering phase. Further down the line the MPC implementation will guarantee a smooth and short commissioning phase for such complex systems, thanks to its adaptive properties.

The deployment of more energy system solutions like this one plays a crucial role towards achieving the goals of a clean energy transition in Europe.

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